

ANNEX I

Glossary

A

Abundance (ecology)

The size of a population of a particular life form in a given area (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Acidification

Ongoing decrease in pH away from neutral value of 7. Often used in reference to oceans, freshwater or soils, as a result of uptake of carbon dioxide from the atmosphere (IPBES core glossary, 2021). See 'Ocean acidification' for a specific definition.

Access and benefit sharing (ABS)

Access and benefit-sharing (ABS) refers to the way in which genetic resources may be accessed, and how the benefits that result from their use are shared between the people or countries using the resources (users) and the people or countries that provide them (providers). In some cases, this also includes valuable traditional knowledge associated with genetic resources that comes from Indigenous Peoples and Local Communities. The benefits to be shared can be monetary, such as sharing royalties when the resources are used to create a commercial product, or non-monetary, such as the development of research skills and knowledge (Convention on Biological Diversity, 2002, 2010b, 2010a).

Adaptation

Adjustment in natural or human systems in response to actual or expected stimuli or their effects, which moderates harm or exploits beneficial opportunities (adapted from IPCC, 2001) as cited in (Burton *et al.*, 2002).

Adaptive capacity

The resilience of an ecological, social or social-ecological system to unexpected or unpredictable shocks (Holling, 2001).

Adaptive management

Adaptive management is defined as a systematic process for continually improving management policies and practices by learning from the outcomes of previously

employed policies and practices and by taking in account the intrinsic changes in the system being managed over time. In active adaptive management, management is treated as a deliberate experiment for purposes of learning by doing.

Aerosol

A collection of solid or liquid particles suspended in a gas. They include dust, smoke, mist, fog, haze, clouds, and smog (Hinds, 1999).

Agricultural intensification

The process of increasing the use of capital, labor, and inputs (e.g., fertilizers, pesticides, machinery) relative to land area, to increase agriculture productivity (EUROSTAT, 2018).

Agrobiodiversity

Agricultural biodiversity includes all components of biological diversity of relevance to food and agriculture, and all components of biological diversity that constitute the agricultural ecosystems, also named agro-ecosystems: the variety and variability of animals, plants and micro-organisms, at the genetic, species and ecosystem levels, which are necessary to sustain key functions of the agro-ecosystem, its structure and processes (Convention on Biological Diversity, 2000).

Agro-ecosystems

An ecosystem, dominated by agriculture, containing assets and functions such as biodiversity, ecological succession and food webs. An agroecosystem is not restricted to the immediate site of agricultural activity (e.g., the farm), but rather includes the region that is impacted by this activity, usually by changes to the complexity of species assemblages and energy flows, as well as to the net nutrient balance (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Agroforestry

Agroforestry is a collective name for land-use systems and technologies where woody perennials (trees, shrubs, palms, bamboos, etc.) are deliberately used on the same land-management units as agricultural crops and animals, in some form of spatial

arrangement or temporal sequence (Choudhury & Jansen, 1999).

Animism

A nature-culture ontology that is defined by the fact that humans acknowledge that non-humans have a different "physicality" or external appearance but that non-humans have an inner self that is similar to humans, which allows exchanges and relationships that may be conflictual or reciprocal (IPBES, 2019).

Aichi Targets

The 20 targets set by the Conference of the Parties to the Convention for Biological Diversity (CBD) at its tenth meeting, under the Strategic Plan for Biodiversity 2011–2020 (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Anthropocene

A proposed term for the present time interval, which recognizes humanity's profound imprint on and role in the functioning of the Earth system. Since it was first proposed in 2000 (Crutzen, 2002; Crutzen & Stoermer, 2000), the term has evolved in breadth and diversity, now ranging from a proposed definition of a new geological epoch, a widely-used metaphor for global change, a novel analytical framework, a meme about the relationship of society to nature, and the framing for new and contested cultural narratives. Different starting periods have been proposed for the geological definition of the Anthropocene, including early agriculture and domestication, colonial species exchange, the onset of the industrial revolution, nuclear bomb deployment in 1945, and the post-WWII period characterized by the great acceleration of global changes and the spread of techno-fossils (Brondizio *et al.*, 2016). A proposal to formalize the 'Anthropocene' as a defined geological unit within the Geological Time Scale remains under discussion by the 'Anthropocene' Working Group for consideration by the International Commission on Stratigraphy (IUGS, 2018).

Anthropocentric

Anthropocentric qualifies an action or a perception of a given situation that is

interpreted by humans or consider humans as the main focus. Nature's contributions to people are fundamentally anthropocentric (IPBES, 2019).

Aquaculture

The farming of aquatic organisms, including fish, mollusks, crustaceans and aquatic plants, in both inland and coastal areas, and involving some form of intervention in the rearing process to enhance production, such as regular stocking, feeding, protection from predators, etc. Farming also implies individual or corporate ownership of the stock being cultivated (FAO, 1997).

Archetypes

In the context of scenarios, an overarching scenario that embodies common characteristics of a number of more specific scenarios (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Assessment reports (in the context of IPBES)

Assessment reports are published outputs of scientific, technical and socioeconomic issues that take into account different approaches, visions and knowledge systems, including global assessments of biodiversity and ecosystem services with a defined geographical scope, and thematic or methodological assessments based on the standard or the fast-track approach. They are to be composed of two or more sections including a summary for policymakers, an optional technical summary and individual chapters and their executive summaries. Assessments are the major output of IPBES, and they contain syntheses of findings on topics that have been selected by the IPBES (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

B

Baseline

A minimum or starting point with which to compare other information (e.g., for comparisons between past and present or before and after an intervention) (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Benefit sharing

Distribution of benefits between stakeholders (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Benefits

Advantage that contributes to well-being from the fulfilment of needs and wants. In the context of Nature's contributions to people (see "Nature's contributions to people"), a benefit is a positive contribution

to the material, relational and subjective aspects of people's life. There may also be negative contributions, dis-benefits, or costs, from Nature, such as diseases (adapted from IPBES, core glossary).

Benthic

Occurring at the bottom of a body of water; related to benthos (NOAA, 2018a).

Bio-prospectors

Exploration of biodiversity for commercially, scientifically, or culturally valuable genetic and biochemical resources (United Nations Environment Programme & United Nations Environment Programme, 2007).

Biocultural diversity

The diversity exhibited by interacting natural systems and cultural (human) systems. The concept rests on three propositions: firstly, that the diversity of life includes human cultures and languages; secondly, that links exist between biodiversity and human cultural diversity; and finally, that these links have developed over time through mutual adaptation and possibly co-evolution between humans, plants and animals (adapted from IPBES, core glossary).

Biodiversity

The variability among living organisms from all sources including terrestrial, marine and other aquatic ecosystems and the ecological complexes of which they are a part. This includes variation in genetic, phenotypic, phylogenetic, and functional attributes, as well as changes in abundance and distribution over time and space within and among species, biological communities and ecosystems (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Biodiversity conservation

The management of human interactions with genes, species, and ecosystems so as to provide the maximum benefit to the present generation while maintaining their potential to meet the needs and aspirations of future generations; encompasses elements of saving, studying, and using biodiversity (WRI *et al.*, 1992).

Biodiversity hotspot

A generic term for an area high in such biodiversity attributes as species richness or endemism (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Biodiversity loss

The reduction of any aspect of biological diversity (i.e. diversity at the genetic, species

and ecosystem levels) that results from loss in a particular area through death (including extinction), destruction or manual removal; it can refer to many scales, from global extinctions to population extinctions, resulting in decreased total diversity at the same scale, adversely affecting human-environment connections and disrupting the flow of Nature's contribution to people (adapted from IPBES, core glossary).

Biodiversity offset

Measurable conservation outcomes resulting from actions designed to compensate for significant residual adverse biodiversity impacts arising from development plans or projects after appropriate prevention and mitigation measures have been taken. The goal of biodiversity offsets is to achieve no net loss and preferably a net gain of biodiversity on the ground with respect to species composition, habitat structure, ecosystem function and people's use and cultural values associated with biodiversity (UNDP, 2016).

Bioeconomy

The bioeconomy is the production, utilization, conservation, and regeneration of biological resources, including related knowledge, science, technology, and innovation, to provide sustainable solutions (information, products, processes and services) within and across all economic sectors and enable a transformation to a sustainable economy (IACBG, 2020).

Bioenergy

Energy generated by combusting solid, liquid or gas fuels made from biomass feedstocks which may or may not have undergone some form of conversion process (Committee on Climate Change, 2011).

Biofuel

Liquid, solid, or gaseous fuel produced by conversion of biomass. Examples include bioethanol from sugar cane or corn, charcoal or woodchips, and biogas from anaerobic decomposition of wastes (OECD, 2002).

Biogeochemistry

The field of biogeochemistry deals with the effect of biological organisms on the chemistry of the Earth (Jørgensen & Fath, 2008).

Biological resources

Biological resources include genetic resources, organisms or parts thereof, populations, or any other biotic component

of ecosystems with actual or potential use or value for humanity (Convention on Biological Diversity, 1992).

Biological sustainable level (fished within)

In fisheries organizations, biological sustainable levels are usually defined according to MSY, which is the Maximum Sustainable Yield (or catch) that can be continuously taken from a stock under existing environmental conditions without affecting its reproductive potential. Two key levels are considered: to assess the sustainability of fishing on a given stock: FMSY which is the fishing mortality that is consistent with achieving MSY and BMSY that is the biomass that results from fishing at FMSY for a long time.

Biomass (ecology)

The mass of non-fossilized and biodegradable organic material in a given area or volume (adapted from IPBES, core glossary).

Biome

A set of naturally occurring communities of plants and animals occupying an environmental and/or climatic domain, defined on a global scale. IPBES biomes, as used in this assessment, are broader and more aggregated than many purely biological classification systems. Where biomes are transformed into anthromes, the 'anthropogenic biomes' of urban areas and cultivated areas have been included. In this assessment we consider (i) wetlands, (ii) inland waters, (iii) coastal systems, (iv) shelf systems, (v) open and deep seas, (vi) urban areas, (vii) rural areas, (viii) grasslands-steppes-savannas, (ix) forests and (x) deserts and mountains (see Chapter 1).

Bioprospecting

The purposeful evaluation of wild biological material in search of valuable new products (Artuso, 2002).

Biosphere

The sum of all the ecosystems of the world. It is both the collection of organisms living on the Earth and the space that they occupy on part of the Earth's crust (the lithosphere), in the oceans (the hydrosphere) and in the atmosphere. The biosphere is all the planet's ecosystems (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Biota

All living organisms of an area; the flora and fauna considered as a unit (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Biotechnology (modern)

Modern biotechnology means the application of:

- a. In vitro nucleic acid techniques, including recombinant deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) and direct injection of nucleic acid into cells or organelles, or
- b. Fusion of cells beyond the taxonomic family,

that overcome natural physiological reproductive or recombination barriers and that are not techniques used in traditional breeding and selection (Convention on Biological Diversity, 2000).

Burden

The resulting negative impacts of ecosystem use and management on people and nature, including distant, diffuse and delayed impacts (modified from Pascual *et al.*, 2017).

Bushmeat

See "wild meat"

Bushmeat hunting

Bushmeat (or wild meat) hunting is a form of hunting that entails the harvesting of wild animals for food and for non-food purposes, including for medicinal use (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Bycatch

The incidental capture of non-target species. The portion of a commercial fishing catch that consists of marine animals caught unintentionally (Merriam-Webster, 2021b).

C

Canned hunting

Hunting of animals in confined enclosures where they are unable to escape (see Chapter 3).

Capacity-building

Defined by the United Nations Development Programme as "the process through which individuals, organizations and societies obtain, strengthen and maintain their capabilities to set and achieve their own development objectives over time" (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Carbon cycle

The flow of carbon (in various forms, e.g., as carbon dioxide (CO₂)) through the atmosphere, ocean, terrestrial and marine biosphere and lithosphere (IPCC, 2014).

Carbon sequestration

The long-term storage of carbon in plants, soils, geologic formations, and the ocean. Carbon sequestration occurs both naturally and as a result of anthropogenic activities and typically refers to the storage of carbon that has the immediate potential to become carbon dioxide gas (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Carbon storage

The biological process by which carbon in the form carbon dioxide is taken up from the atmosphere and incorporated through photosynthesis into different compartments of ecosystems, such as biomass, wood, or soil organic carbon. Also, the technological process of capturing waste carbon dioxide from industry or power generation, and storing it so that it will not enter the atmosphere (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Carrying capacity

In ecology, the carrying capacity of a species in an environment is the maximum population size of the species that the environment can sustain indefinitely. The term is also used more generally to refer to the upper limit of habitats, ecosystems, landscapes, waterscapes or seascapes to provide tangible and intangible goods and services (including aesthetic and spiritual services) in a sustainable way (IPBES, 2019).

Ceremonial uses (of wild species)

Ceremonial uses are defined as uses of wild species in spiritual observances and practices valued for their role in maintaining cultural identity and social reproduction.

Certainty

In the context of IPBES, the summary terms to describe the state of knowledge are the following:

- Well established (Certainty term (q.v.)): comprehensive meta-analysis or other synthesis or multiple independent studies that agree.
- Established but incomplete (Certainty term (q.v.)): general agreement although only a limited number of studies exist but no comprehensive synthesis and, or the studies that exist imprecisely address the question.
- Unresolved (Certainty term (q.v.)): multiple independent studies exist but conclusions do not agree.

- Inconclusive (Certainty term (q.v.)): limited evidence, recognizing major knowledge gaps.

(IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Certification (environmental)

A procedure by which a third party gives written assurance that a product, process or service is in conformity with certain environmental standards (Dankers, 2003).

Charismatic species

Species that has a privileged value for a group (academic or not academic) and is used to focus attention on conservation campaigns (in the case of NGOs and environmentalists) or considered as a heritage (3 characters: inherited from ancestor, supposed to be transmitted to the next generation, sustainably managed) and in which the group identifies him-self (Cormier-Salem *et al.*, 2005; Cormier-Salem & Bassett, 2007; Dounias, 2007; Lizet & Milliet, 2012; Posey, 1999).

Citizen science

Citizen science refers to research collaborations in which volunteers and scientists partner to answer real-world questions, typically through a connected interface. A major setback of citizen science projects is that they require some level of computer literacy and network connectivity, both rare in many rural areas of the developing world. Despite the challenge, some researchers have already been successful in implementing interactive multimedia web-based tools for the collection of data based on local monitoring systems (Ens, 2012; Gill & Lantz, 2014; Pulsifer *et al.*, 2010; Stevens *et al.*, 2014).

Climate change

As defined in Article 1 of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change, "a change of climate which is attributed directly or indirectly to human activity that alters the composition of the global atmosphere and which is in addition to natural climate variability observed over comparable time periods" (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Collapse (socioecological system)

The rapid and durable loss of a defined socio-ecological system as such, resulting in substantial loss of social-ecological capital (e.g., biomass) (Cumming & Peterson, 2017).

Collecting

See "Gathering".

Co-management

Process of management in which government shares power with resource users, with each given specific rights and responsibilities relating to information and decision-making (OECD, 2007a) (also see Chapter 6).

Common Property Theory (CPT)

Common property theory (CPT) refers to a body of cross-disciplinary literature that deals with the historical and contemporary institutional governance and management of valued resources ranging from fisheries and forests to atmospheric sinks, oceans, and genetic materials. CPT was originally developed to understand the problems of managing what are termed common-pool resources (Pokrant, 2011).

Community (ecological)

An assemblage of populations of at least two different species which coexist, and to various degrees interact directly and indirectly within a defined local geographic area and in a particular time; it is characterized in terms of taxonomic and functional composition (the species and functional types present) and richness (e.g., richness, abundance, dominance and distribution of species, or phenotypes) (Stroud *et al.*, 2015).

Community (social)

A group of people who inhabit or perform ongoing activities in a shared geographic space, who interact with one another, share similar values, identity, and heritage that form a basis for communal rules regulating collective behavior (MacQueen *et al.*, 2001; McGoodwin, 2001).

Community forestry

A broad term used to describe models of forest management that give local people the majority say in making decisions. Similar terms include participatory forest management, collaborative forest management, social forestry, and community-based forest management. With an aim to reduce poverty, community forestry is participatory and should serve all community members equitably (IPBES, 2019).

Community-based natural resource management

An approach to natural resource

management that involves the full participation of indigenous peoples' and local communities and resource users in decision-making activities, and the incorporation of local institutions, customary practices, and knowledge systems in management, regulatory, and enforcement processes. Under this approach, community-based monitoring and information systems are initiatives by indigenous peoples and local community organizations to monitor their community's well-being and the state of their territories and natural resources, applying a mix of traditional knowledge and innovative tools and approaches (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Community-based tourism

Community-based tourism is defined as an approach to tourism development which prioritizes the needs and desires of the host community.

Community-managed forests

Decentralized system of forest resource management designed to promote more equitable outcomes for stakeholders' livelihoods changing relationships between stakeholders and government agencies (adapted from Newton *et al.*, 2015).

Conflict

Conflict is defined as when levels of armed violence due to political insecurity, instability, or civil or international war are substantially higher than in non-conflict times. This leads to a disruption of economies, government services and the extensive movement of people to flee conflict zones for personal safety and/or better opportunities (see Chapter 4).

Conservation benefits

The positive impacts on people and ecosystems due to conservation (IPBES, 2019).

Conservation biology

The branch of biological science concerned with the conservation, management, and protection of vulnerable species, populations, and ecosystems. Also see 'Biological conservation' (IPBES, 2019).

Co-production (of contributions between nature and people)

In the context of the IPBES conceptual framework, this is the joint contribution by nature and anthropogenic assets in generating Nature's contributions to people (IPBES, 2016c).

Cross-sectoral

Relating to interactions between sectors (that is, the distinct parts of society, or of a nation's economy), such as how one sector affects another sector, or how a factor affects two or more sectors (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Cultural change (or cultural transformation)

Cultural change is a continuous process in any society, which can vary from gradual to stochastic, resulting from interactions between processes that are internal (ex. needs, local changes, crisis, mobility, ideas, invention and innovation, conflicts, etc.) and external (ex. diffusion, external agents, political and economic forces, conflicts, etc.) (Berry, 2008; Redfield *et al.*, 1936). Cultural change is interpreted differently depending on theoretical orientation, such as diffusionism, modernization theory, world system theory, neocolonialism, globalization, among others (see Peña, 2005; Rudmin, 2009; Santos-Granero, 2009). Culture change can be selective or systemic and most often involves resistance and conflicts but can also lead to adaptation and resilience in changing contexts and environments.

Cultural ecosystem services

A category of ecosystem services first developed in the Millenium Ecosystem Assessment (2005) to refer to the nonmaterial benefits people obtain from ecosystems through spiritual enrichment, cognitive development, reflection, recreation, and aesthetic experience, including, e.g., knowledge systems, social relations, and aesthetic values (Millenium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005). In this assessment, cultural ecosystem services are included as part of both material and non-material Nature's contributions to people.

Cultural diversity

As stated in the UNESCO Universal Declaration on Cultural Diversity, "Culture takes diverse forms across time and space. This diversity is embodied in the uniqueness and plurality of the identities of the groups and societies making up humankind. As a source of exchange, innovation and creativity, cultural diversity is as necessary for humankind as biodiversity is for nature. In this sense, it is the common heritage of humanity and should be recognized and affirmed for the benefit of present and future generations...Cultural diversity widens the range of options open to everyone; it is one

of the roots of development, understood not simply in terms of economic growth, but also as a means to achieve a more satisfactory intellectual, emotional, moral and spiritual existence." (UNESCO, 2001).

Cultural continuity

Cultural continuity has been conceptualized within Indigenous health research that builds on cultural connectedness to emphasize the importance of intergenerational cultural connectedness, which is maintained through intact families and the engagement of elders, who pass traditions to subsequent generations. Cultural continuity also situates culture as being dynamic through the maintenance of collective memory, which may change over time (Auger, 2016) (see Chapter 3).

Cultural identity

Cultural identity is the identity or feeling of belonging to, as part of the self-conception and self-perception to nationality, ethnicity, religion, social class, generation, locality and any kind of social group that have its own distinct culture. In this way that cultural identity is both characteristic of the individual but also to the culturally identical group that has its members sharing the same cultural identity (see Chapter 3).

Cultural keystone species / culturally important species

Culturally keystone species designate species whose existence and symbolic value shape in a major way and over time, the cultural identity of a people, as reflected in the fundamental roles these species have in diet, materials, medicine, and/or spiritual practices (Cristancho & Vining, 2004; Garibaldi & Turner, 2004).

Cultural landscapes

Cultural landscapes express the long-term co-evolution and relationships between people and nature, influenced by internal and external forces affecting the aesthetic and productive configuration of land management, water bodies, wildlife, property systems, infrastructure and human settlements, and which are both a source and a product of changing social, institutional, economic, and cultural systems (also see World Heritage Centre, 2008).

Cultural values

Cultural values are shared social values and norms, which are learned and dynamic, and which underpin attitudes and behavior and how people respond to events and

opportunities, and affects the hierarchy of values people assign to objects, knowledge, stories, feelings, other beings, forms of social expressions, and behaviors (IPBES, 2019).

Culture

Culture is defined as a key determinant of, for example, what is defined as suitable food and preferred approaches to supporting human health.

Customary land tenure

The socially-embedded systems and institutions used within communities to regulate and manage land use and access, and which derive from the community itself rather than from the state (IPBES, 2019).

Customary law / norms

Law consisting of customs that are accepted as legal requirements or obligatory rules of conduct; practices and beliefs that are so vital and intrinsic a part of a social and economic system that they are treated as if they were laws (Convention on Biological Diversity, 2018).

Customary rights

Rights, such as land rights or political rights, that are granted by either customary or statutory law. Customary rights exist where there is a consensus of relevant actors considering them to be 'law' (IPBES, 2019).

Customary sustainable use

Uses of biological resources in accordance with traditional cultural practices that are compatible with conservation or sustainable use requirements (Convention on Biological Diversity, 2018).

D**Decomposition**

Breakdown of complex organic substances into simpler molecules or ions by physical, chemical and/or biological processes. (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Decorative and aesthetic uses

Decorative and aesthetic uses are defined as the uses of wild species in order to produce handicrafts and objects of adornment, beauty, and/or entertainment.

Deforestation

Human-induced conversion of forested land to non-forested land. Deforestation can be permanent, when this change is definitive or temporary when this change is part of

a cycle that includes natural or assisted regeneration (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Demographic change (or demographic transition)

A model describing transition in demographic profile of a population, which has been associated with the development process that transforms an agricultural society into an industrial one and characterized by a rapid population growth due to a decline in the death rate while fertility remains high initially; the growth rate then declines due to a decline in the birth rate. Before the transition's onset, population growth is low as high death rates tend to offset high fertility. After the transition, population growth is again below replacement level as both birth and death rates reach low levels (Bongaarts, 2009).

Desertification

Desertification means land degradation in arid, semi-arid and dry subhumid areas resulting from various factors, including climatic variations and human activities. Desertification does not refer to the natural expansion of existing deserts (UNCCD, 1994).

Dispersal

Movement of individuals (and in some species, their gametes) that has the potential for moving genes through space (Templeton, 2017).

Domesticated species

Species in which the evolutionary process has been influenced by humans to meet their needs (Convention on Biological Diversity, 1992).

Domestication

Evolutionary process driven by human (whether conscious or unconscious) selection but also involving natural processes applied to wild plants or animals and leading to adaptation to cultivation and consumption or utilization. Domestication can be complete, whereby organisms become entirely dependent on humans for their continued existence or can be partial or incipient, whereby they still reproduce independently of human intervention (Gepts, 2014). In traditional systems, farmer practices still shape the genetic structure of crops and their evolution (Vigouroux *et al.*, 2011).

Drivers

For the purpose of this assessment, drivers are defined as the factors that, directly

or indirectly influence the sustainability of use of wild species, by changing the abundance or distribution of species in use, altering demand on and consumption of wild species, products derived from wild species and/or changing the (nature, scale, and/or intensity of) interactions with wild species in use (practices). It is recognized that the same factor may influence different components of the system (wild species, practices, Nature's contributions to people); and the interactions among these factors vary across time and space, which can have negative or positive effects on sustainability (see Chapter 4).

Drivers of change

Drivers of change refer to all those external factors that affect nature, and, as a consequence, also affect the supply of Nature's contributions to people. The IPBES conceptual framework includes drivers of change as two of its main elements: indirect drivers, which are all anthropogenic, and direct drivers, both natural and anthropogenic (IPBES, 2019).

Drylands

Drylands comprise arid, semi-arid and dry sub-humid areas. The term excludes hyper-arid areas, also known as deserts. Drylands are characterized by water scarcity and cover approximately 40% of the world's terrestrial surface (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

E

Ecolabelling

Ecolabelling is defined as a voluntary approach to environmental certification practiced around the world. Ecolabel is defined as a product that meets a wide range of environmental performance criteria or standards (Golden *et al.*, 2010).

Ecological footprint

A measure of the amount of biologically productive land and water required to support the demands of a population or productive activity. Ecological footprints can be calculated at any scale: for an activity, a person, a community, a city, a region, a nation or humanity as a whole (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Ecological (or socio-ecological) breakpoint or threshold

The point at which a relatively small change in external conditions causes a rapid change in an ecosystem. When an ecological

threshold has been passed, the ecosystem may no longer be able to return to its state by means of its inherent resilience (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Economic and financial instruments

see "Policy instruments".

Ecosystem

The ecosystem is defined in this assessment as the largest functional unit that includes both living organisms and the abiotic environment, each influencing the properties of the other, and the two being necessary to maintain life as it exists on Earth (Odum, 1953).

Ecosystem approach

See "Ecosystem-based approach".

Ecosystem degradation

A long-term reduction in an ecosystem's structure, functionality, or capacity to provide benefits to people (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Ecosystem function

The flow of energy and materials through the biotic and abiotic components of an ecosystem. It includes many processes such as biomass production, trophic transfer through plants and animals, nutrient cycling, water dynamics and heat transfer (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Ecosystem ecology

The integrated study of biotic and abiotic components of ecosystems and their interactions within an ecosystem framework. This science examines physical and biological structures and examines how these ecosystem characteristics interact with each other (Simon *et al.*, 2010).

Ecosystem health

Ecosystem health is a metaphor used to describe the condition of an ecosystem, by analogy with human health. Note that there is no universally accepted benchmark for a healthy ecosystem. Rather, the apparent health status of an ecosystem can vary, depending upon which metrics are employed in judging it, and which societal aspirations are driving the assessment (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Ecosystem management

An approach to maintaining or restoring the composition, structure, function, and delivery of services of natural and modified ecosystems for the goal of

achieving sustainability. It is based on an adaptive, collaboratively developed vision of desired future conditions that integrates ecological, socioeconomic, and institutional perspectives, applied within a geographic framework, and defined primarily by natural ecological boundaries (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Ecosystem services

The benefits people obtain from ecosystems. In the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, ecosystem services can be divided into supporting, regulating, provisioning and cultural. This classification, however, is superseded in IPBES assessments by the system used under "Nature's contributions to people". This is because IPBES recognizes that many services fit into more than one of the four categories. For example, food is both a provisioning service and also, emphatically, a cultural service, in many cultures (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Ecosystem-based approach

A strategy for the integrated management of land, water and living resources that promotes conservation and sustainable use in an equitable way. An ecosystem approach is based on the application of appropriate scientific methods, focused on levels of biological organization that encompass the essential structure, processes, functions and interactions among and between organisms and their environment. It recognizes that humans, with their cultural diversity, are an integral component of many ecosystems (UNEP, 2012).

Edge effect

A change in species composition, physical conditions or ecological factors at the boundary between two or more habitats (IUCN, 2012a).

El Niño / La Niña

The term El Niño was initially used to describe a warm-water current that periodically flows along the coast of Ecuador and Perú, disrupting the local fishery. It has since become identified with a basin-wide warming of the tropical Pacific Ocean east of the dateline. This oceanic event is associated with a fluctuation of a global-scale tropical and subtropical surface pressure pattern called the Southern Oscillation. This coupled atmosphere-ocean phenomenon, with preferred time scales of two to about seven years, is collectively

known as the El Niño-Southern Oscillation (ENSO) (IPCC, 2014).

Empowerment

The process by which people gain control over the factors and decisions that shape their lives. It is the process by which they increase their assets and attributes and build capacities to gain access, partners, networks and/or a voice, in order to gain control (WHO, 2010).

Enabling conditions

Enabling conditions are defined as conditions that facilitate approaches to addressing social and ecological challenges. They can be defined as factors that increase the likelihood of an intended change in the governance approach, strategy, or management regime. The presence of enabling conditions can facilitate the emergence of a particular environmental policy, whereas the absence of key enabling conditions can present a barrier to management or sustained policy action (Huber-Stearns *et al.*, 2017). See Chapter 6.

Endangered species

A species at risk of extinction in the wild (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Endemic species

Species that is native to, and restricted to, a particular geographical region. Highly endemic species, those with very restricted natural ranges, are especially vulnerable to extinction if their natural habitat is eliminated or significantly disturbed (IUCN, 2012a).

Energy security

Access to clean, reliable and affordable energy services for cooking and heating, lighting, communications and productive uses (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Energy source

Primary energy sources take many forms, including nuclear energy, fossil energy -like oil, coal and natural gas- and renewable sources like wind, solar, geothermal and hydropower. These primary sources are converted to electricity, a secondary energy source (US Department of Energy, 2018).

Environmental education

The facilitation of an integrated perception of the problems of the environment, enabling more rational actions capable of meeting social needs to be taken (UNESCO, 1978).

Environmental governance

Environmental governance, as a subclass of the broader governance concept, has been defined as "the set of regulatory processes, mechanisms and organizations through which political actors influence environmental actions and outcomes" (Lemos & Agrawal, 2006), and it "should be understood broadly so as to include all institutional solutions for resolving conflicts over environmental resources" (Paavola, 2007).

Environmental gradients

Environmental characteristics that explain the distribution of organisms and ecosystems in terms of environmental tolerances (Government of New Brunswick, 2007).

Environmental Impact Assessment

A formal, evidence-based procedure that assesses the economic, social, and environmental effects of public policy or of any human activity (IPBES, 2019).

Environmental justice

The fair treatment and meaningful involvement of all people regardless of race, color, national origin, or income with respect to the development, implementation and enforcement of environmental laws, regulations and policies (EPA, 2018).

Essential Biodiversity Variables (EBVs)

Essential Biodiversity Variables are promoted by the Group on Earth Observations Biodiversity Observation Network (GEO BON). The idea behind this concept is to identify, using a systems approach, the key variables that should be monitored in order to measure biodiversity change. The Essential Biodiversity Variables are an intermediate layer of abstraction between raw data, from *in situ* and remote sensing observations, and derived high-level indicators used to communicate the state and trends of biodiversity (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Ethnobiology

The study of dynamic relationships among peoples, biota, and environments, as encoded in the knowledge held by different societies and individuals. Its multidisciplinary nature allows it to examine complex, dynamic interactions between human and natural systems, and enhances our intellectual merit and broader impacts (Society of Ethnobiology, 2018).

Eutrophication

An enrichment of water by nutrients that causes structural changes to the ecosystem, such as: increased production of algae and aquatic plants, depletion of fish species, general deterioration of water quality and other effects that reduce and preclude use (OECD, 1982).

Evolutionary biology

A sub-discipline of the biological sciences concerned with the origin of life and the diversification and adaptation of life forms over time (Nature, 2018).

Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ)

An Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ) is a concept adopted at the Third United Nations Conference on the Law of the Sea (1982), whereby a coastal State assumes jurisdiction over the exploration and exploitation of marine resources in its adjacent section of the continental shelf, taken to be a band extending 200 miles from the shore. The Exclusive Economic Zone comprises an area which extends either from the coast or in federal systems from the seaward boundaries of the constituent states (3 to 12 nautical miles, in most cases) to 200 nautical miles (370 kilometers) off the coast. Within this area, nations claim and exercise sovereign rights and exclusive fishery management authority over all fish and all Continental Shelf fishery resources (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Exploitation

The consumptive use of any natural resources (Groom *et al.*, 2006).

Exploratory scenarios

(also known as “explorative scenarios” or “descriptive scenarios”)

Scenarios that examine a range of plausible futures, based on potential trajectories of drivers – either indirect (e.g., socio-political, economic and technological factors) or direct (e.g., habitat conversion, climate change) (IPBES, 2016c)

Externality

A positive or negative consequence (benefits or costs) of an action that affects someone other than the agent undertaking that action and for which the agent is neither compensated nor penalized through the markets (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Extinction

A population, species or more inclusive taxonomic group has gone extinct when

all its individuals have died. A species may go extinct locally (population extinction), regionally (e.g., extinction of all populations in a country, continent or ocean) or globally. Populations or species reduced to such low numbers that they are no longer of economic or functional importance may be said to have gone economically or functionally extinct, respectively. Species extinctions are typically not documented immediately: for example, the IUCN Red List categories and criteria require there to be no reasonable doubt that all individuals have died, before a species is formally listed as Extinct (see IUCN Red List) (IUCN, 2012b).

Extractive practices

Extractive practices are defined as the temporary or permanent removal of organisms, part of them or materials derived from them, and may result in mortality of the individual to be used (e.g., hunting or whole plant harvest), but does not necessarily do so (e.g., limited collection of plant propagules or shearing and releasing of vicuna) (see Chapter 1).

F

Fallow

Land normally used for production and left to recover for part or all of a growing season (more in the case of swidden agriculture) (Gleave, 1996; United Nations, 1997).

Feedback

The modification or control of a process or system by its results or effects (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Feral

Species are considered to be feral if they or their ancestors were formerly domesticated, but they are now living independently of humans (modified from FAO, 2021)

Fishery

Generally, a fishery is an activity leading to harvesting of fish. It may involve capture of wild fish or raising of fish through aquaculture (FAO, 2021). Note that in this definition, the term fish includes all types of marine animals, fish, but also crustaceans, mollusks, echinoderms etc.

Fishing

Fishing is defined as the removal from their habitats of aquatic animals (vertebrates and invertebrates) that spend their full life cycle in water (e.g., fish, some marine mammals, shellfish, shrimps, squids, corals). Fishing

most often results in the death of the aquatic animal, but it may not in some cases. To reflect both situations, fishing has been sub-divided into a lethal and a “non-lethal” category. Lethal fishing is defined as the general and more usual meaning of fishing that leads to the killing of the animal, such as in traditional commercial fisheries. “Non-lethal fishing is defined as the temporary or permanent capture of live animals from their habitat without intended mortality, such as in aquarium fish trade or catch and release. However, unintended mortality may occur in “non-lethal” fishing and the term “non-lethal” is therefore put in quotes. The killing of species that spend part of their life cycle in terrestrial environments (e.g., walrus, sea turtles) is encompassed by the definition of hunting (see Chapter 1).

Fitness (ecology)

Fitness involves the ability of organisms – or populations or species – to survive and reproduce in the environment in which they find themselves, and thus contribute genes to the next generation (Orr, 2009).

Folk medicine

Folk medicine is defined as the mixture of traditional healing practices and beliefs that involve use of algae, animals, fungi, and plants, spirituality and manual therapies or exercises in order to diagnose, treat or prevent an ailment or illness (adapted from WHO, 2008).

Food security

The World Food Summit of 1996 defined food security as existing “when all people at all times have access to sufficient, safe, nutritious food to maintain a healthy and active life” (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Food-web

An important ecological concept representing feeding relationships within a community and implying the transfer of food energy from its source in plants through herbivores to carnivores; normally, food webs consist of a number of food chains meshed together (Hui, 2012).

Forest

A vegetation type dominated by trees. Definitions of forest varies according to the use of parameters such as biogeography, physiognomy, biomass, human management, species dominance and composition, among others, therefore affecting estimates of extent and type of change (also see IPCC, 2014).

Forest degradation

A process leading to a temporary or permanent deterioration in the density or structure of vegetation cover or its species composition. It is a change in forest attributes that leads to a lower productive capacity caused by an increase in disturbances. Continued degradation of the forests can destroy the entire forest cover and biodiversity, and it mainly occurs because of environmental and anthropogenic changes (Tejawasi, 2007).

Forest management

Forest management is defined as a practice about managing, using, conserving and repairing forest, woodlands and associated resources. Objectives and goals are fulfilled by implementing and regulating tree management and harvesting practices stipulated in forest management plans (see Chapter 3).

Fossil fuel

Fossil fuels are derived from the remains of ancient plant and animal life: coal, oil and natural gas. In common dialogue, the term fossil fuel also includes hydrocarbon-containing natural resources that are not derived from animal or plant sources (OECD, 2001a).

Free, prior and informed consent (FPIC)

Free implies that Indigenous Peoples and Local Communities are not pressured, intimidated, manipulated or unduly influenced and that their consent is given, without coercion; prior implies seeking consent or approval sufficiently in advance of any authorization to access traditional knowledge respecting the customary decision-making processes in accordance with national legislation and time requirements of Indigenous Peoples and Local Communities; informed implies that information is provided that covers relevant aspects, such as: the intended purpose of the access; its duration and scope; a preliminary assessment of the likely economic, social, cultural and environmental impacts, including potential risks; personnel likely to be involved in the execution of the access; procedures the access may entail and benefit-sharing arrangements; consent or approval is the agreement of the Indigenous Peoples and Local Communities who are holders of traditional knowledge or the competent authorities of those Indigenous Peoples and Local Communities, as appropriate, to grant

access to their traditional knowledge to a potential user and includes the right not to grant consent or approval. (modified from Convention on Biological Diversity, 2018).

Functional diversity

The range, values, relative abundance and distribution of functional traits in a given community or ecosystem (Díaz *et al.*, 2007).

Functional group

A collection of organisms with similar suites of co-occurring functional attributes. Groups are traditionally associated with similar responses to external factors and/or effects on ecosystem processes. A functional group is often referred to as 'guild', especially when referring to animals, e.g., the feeding types of aquatic organisms having the same function within the trophic chain (De Bello *et al.*, 2010).

G**Gathering**

Gathering is defined as the removal of terrestrial and aquatic algae, fungi, and plants (other than trees) or parts thereof from their habitats. Gathering may, but often does not, result in the death of the organism. Gathering includes whole plant harvest and removal of above and/or below ground plant parts, as well as the fruiting bodies of macrofungi. It also includes removal of non-woody portions of trees (e.g., leaves, propagules, and bark). Where removal of propagules or death of an individual plant occurs (e.g., whole plant and root removal) effects on population sustainability are contingent upon factors including timing, frequency, and intensity of harvest. The harvest of wood and woody parts of trees is encompassed by the definition of logging (see Chapter 1).

Gender

The term gender refers to the socially-constructed expectations about the characteristics, aptitudes and behaviors associated with being a woman or a man. Gender defines what is feminine and masculine. Gender shapes the social roles that men and women play and the power relations between them, which can have a profound effect on the use and management of natural resources.

Gender is not based on sex or the biological differences between women and men; rather, gender is shaped by culture and social norms. Thus, depending on values,

norms, customs and laws, women and men in different parts of the world have adopted different gender roles and relations. Within the same society, gender roles also differ by race/ethnicity, class/caste, religion, ethnicity, age and economic circumstances. Gender and gender roles then affect the economic, political, social, and ecological opportunities and constraints faced by both women and men (Convention on Biological Diversity, 2017). The framing of sex and gender as binaries is in fact a cultural ideology. The empirical reality is that sex is a spectrum, manifesting in a wide array of sex variance. Some people don't neatly fit into the categories of "man" or "woman," or "male" or "female." For example, some people have a gender that blends elements of being a man or a woman, or a gender that is different than either male or female. Some people don't identify with any gender, or their gender changes over time.

Gene

The basic physical and functional unit of heredity. Genes are made up of DNA, and occupy a fixed position (locus) on a chromosome. Genes achieve their effects by directing the synthesis of proteins (Encyclopaedia Britannica, 2018).

Generalist species

A species able to thrive in a wide variety of environmental conditions and that can make use of a variety of different resources (for example, a flower visiting insect that lives on the floral resources provided by several to many different plants) (IPBES, 2019).

Genetic diversity

The variation at the level of individual genes, which provides a mechanism for populations to adapt to their ever-changing environment. The more variation, the better the chance that at least some of the individuals will have an allelic variant that is suited for the new environment, and will produce offspring with the variant that will in turn reproduce and continue the population into subsequent generations (NBII, 2011).

Genetic manipulation or genetic engineering

The artificial manipulation, modification, and recombination of DNA or other nucleic acid molecules in order to modify an organism or population of organisms (IPBES, 2019).

Genetic resources

Genetic material of actual or potential value (Convention on Biological Diversity, 1992).

Genetically Modified Organism (GMO)

The Cartagena Protocol on Biosafety defines 'living modified organism' as any living organism that possesses a novel combination of genetic material obtained through the use of modern biotechnology (Convention on Biological Diversity, 2000).

Global commons or global common pool resources (CPR)

Global commons are resources at a planetary scale that are outside national jurisdictions. International law identifies four global commons: the high seas; the atmosphere; Antarctica; and outer space, which are recognized as the common heritage of humankind (UNEP Division of Environmental Law and Conventions) (Nakicenovic *et al.*, 2016).

Global North – Global South

The Global South and the Global North is a terminology that distinguishes not only between political systems or degrees of poverty, but between the victims and the benefactors of global capitalism (Wolters *et al.*, 2015).

Good Quality of Life (GQL)

Within the context of the IPBES Conceptual Framework – the achievement of a fulfilled human life, a notion which may vary strongly across different societies and groups within societies. It is a context-dependent state of individuals and human groups, comprising aspects such as access to food, water, energy and livelihood security, and also health, good social relationships and equity, security, cultural identity, and freedom of choice and action. "Living in harmony with nature", "living-well in balance and harmony with Mother Earth" and "human well-being" are examples of different perspectives on a "Good quality of life" (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Governance

A comprehensive and inclusive concept of the full range of means for deciding, managing, implementing and monitoring policies and measures. Whereas government is defined strictly in terms of the nation-state, the more inclusive concept of governance recognizes the contributions of various levels of government (global, international, regional, sub-national and local) and the contributing roles of the private sector, of nongovernmental actors, and of civil society to addressing the many types of issues facing the global community (IPCC, 2018).

Governance (modes of)

'Modes of governance' have been conceptualized in different ways, from hierarchies (state centric governance), networks or co-governance (a constellation of actors in varying partnership arrangements), markets (market-based instruments and incentives), voluntarism (non-binding agreements and instruments) and self-governance (including customary governance) (Sowman & Wynberg, 2014).

Grabbing (of wild species and spaces)

Actions, policies or initiatives by which use and access rights of resources and spaces are transferred and re-allocated from collective entity to private or public entity, leading to IPLC dispossession, marginalization and exclusion and, consequently, the unsustainability of use system (Acheson, 2015; Fairhead *et al.*, 2012; National Research Council & National Research Council (U.S.), 2002). These processes of control (whether through ownership, lease, concession, contracts, quotas, or general power) as well as commons enclosure, have two main purposes: on the one hand, productivist exploitation (speculation, extraction, land stewardship, food sovereignty); on the other hand, conservation (e.g. Protected Areas, no-take' conservation areas, restoration of endangered habitat, resource control or nature commodification, Biodiversity offsets, REDD+, etc.), qualified either green for land conservation (Benabou, 2014), or blue for ocean conservation (Bennett *et al.*, 2020; Clark Howard, 2018; Cormier-Salem & Bassett, 2007). Moreover, the commons, or common pool resources, cover a large set of assets, from wild species to habitats and institutions, either terrestrial and referred as large-scale land acquisition (Baker-Smith & Attila, 2016) and land grabbing, or aquatic, oceanic and coastal and referred as water (Duvail *et al.*, 2012) or ocean grabbing (Artaud & Surrallés, 2017; Bennett *et al.*, 2020).

Grassland

Type of biome characterized by a more or less closed herbaceous (non-woody) vegetation layer, sometimes with a shrub layer, but – in contrast to savannas – without, or with very few, trees. Different types of grasslands are found under a broad range of climatic conditions (modified from IPBES, core glossary).

Grazing

Feeding on growing herbage, attached algae, or phytoplankton (Merriam-Webster, 2021a).

Green bonds

A mode of private financing that tap the debt capital market through fixed income instruments (i.e., bonds) to raise capital to finance climate-friendly projects in key sectors of, but not limited to, transport, energy, building and industry, water, agriculture and forestry and waste (OECD, 2015).

Green hunting

Green hunting occurs with tranquilizer dart guns and the animals are released alive. This is typically performed for veterinary procedures or translocation, and has been suggested as an alternative to lethal forms of hunting (Greyling *et al.*, 2004).

Green Revolution

Period of food crop productivity growth that started in the 1960s due to a combination of high rates of investment in crop research, infrastructure, and market development and appropriate policy support, and whose environmental impacts have been mixed: on one side saving land conversion to agriculture, on the other side promoting an overuse of inputs and cultivation on areas otherwise improper to high levels of intensification, such as slopes (Pingali, 2012).

Greenhouse gases (GHGs)

Greenhouse gases are those gaseous constituents of the atmosphere, both natural and anthropogenic, that absorb and emit radiation at specific wavelengths within the spectrum of terrestrial radiation emitted by the Earth's surface, the atmosphere itself, and by clouds. This property causes the greenhouse effect. Water vapour (H₂O), carbon dioxide (CO₂), nitrous oxide (N₂O), methane (CH₄) and ozone (O₃) are the primary greenhouse gases in the Earth's atmosphere. Moreover, there are a number of entirely human-made greenhouse gases in the atmosphere, such as the halocarbons and other chlorine- and bromine containing substances, dealt with under the Montreal Protocol. Beside CO₂, N₂O and CH₄, the Kyoto Protocol deals with the greenhouse gases sulphur hexafluoride (SF₆), hydrofluorocarbons (HFCs) and perfluorocarbons (PFCs) (IPCC, 2014).

H**Habitat**

The place or type of site where an organism or population naturally occurs. Also used to mean the environmental attributes required by a particular species or its ecological niche (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Habitat degradation

A general term describing the set of processes by which habitat quality is reduced. Habitat degradation may occur through natural processes (e.g., drought, heat, cold) and through human activities (forestry, agriculture, urbanization). It is sometimes used as a synonym of habitat deterioration or nature deterioration (IPBES, 2019).

Habitat fragmentation

A general term describing the set of processes by which habitat loss results in the division of continuous habitats into a greater number of smaller patches of lesser total and isolated from each other by a matrix of dissimilar habitats. Habitat fragmentation may occur through natural processes (e.g., forest and grassland fires, flooding) and through human activities (forestry, agriculture, urbanization) (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Habitat loss

A general term describing the set of processes by which habitat quality is reduced. Habitat degradation may occur through natural processes (e.g., drought, heat, cold) and through human activities (forestry, agriculture, urbanization) (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Harmonization

The process of bringing together, and comparing, models or scenarios to make them compatible or consistent with one another (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Hazard

A process, phenomenon or human activity that may cause loss of life, injury or other health impacts, property damage, social and economic disruption or environmental degradation. Hazards that this assessment discusses are mostly environmental hazards (chemical, natural and biological hazards), while cognizant that many hazards are socio-natural, in that they are associated with a combination of natural and anthropogenic factors. Natural hazards are predominantly associated with natural processes and phenomena, including geological or geophysical hazards that originate from internal earth processes (earthquakes, volcanic activities, landslides, tsunamis), and hydrometeorological hazards, which are of atmospheric, hydrological or oceanographic origin (tropical cyclones, floods, drought; heatwaves, and storm surges). Biological

hazards are of organic origin or conveyed by biological vectors, including pathogenic microorganisms, toxins and bioactive substances. Examples are bacteria, viruses or parasites, as well as venomous wildlife and insects, poisonous plants and mosquitoes carrying disease-causing agents (UNISDR, 2015).

Homegarden

Yard areas surrounding a house for vegetable and fruit production and keeping of domestic animals. In many regions homegardens contain wild species utilized as medicinal plants, timber or other uses (M. Walker *et al.*, 2009).

Homogenization

When used in the ecological sense “homogenization” means a decrease in the extent to which communities differ in species or functional composition (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Human history

A general term used to refer to pre-historical and historical periods describing the development of humanity. Different classifications of periods exist reflecting different interpretation of human history (IPBES, 2019).

Horticulture

High investment crop production using resources intensively for high value product (FAO, 2013).

Hypoxia

Low dissolved oxygen levels in coastal and oceanic waters (<2mL per liter of water), either naturally occurring or as a result of a degradation (e.g., eutrophication) (Altieri *et al.*, 2017; Diaz & Rosenberg, 2008).

I**Identity**

The ways in which people understand who they are, their belonging and role in society, and their relation to their broader environment (Fearon, 1999; Ingalls & Stedman, 2017).

Illegal practices

Illegal is defined in the context of this assessment when it violates laws and regulations.

Illegal, unreported and unregulated (IUU) fishing

A broad term which includes: fishing

and fishing-related activities conducted in contravention of national, regional and international laws; non-reporting, misreporting or under-reporting of information on fishing operations and their catches; fishing by “Stateless” vessels; fishing in convention areas of Regional Fisheries Management Organizations (RFMOs) by non-party vessels; fishing activities which are not regulated by States and cannot be easily monitored and accounted for (FAO, 2016).

Impact assessment

A formal, evidence-based procedure that assesses the economic, social, and environmental effects of public policy or of any human activity (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

In situ conservation of biodiversity

The conservation of ecosystems and natural habitats and the maintenance and recovery of viable populations of species in their natural surroundings and, in the case of domesticated or cultivated species, in the surroundings where they have developed their distinctive properties (Convention on Biological Diversity, 1992).

Indicators

A quantitative or qualitative factor or variable that provides a simple, measurable and quantifiable characteristic or attribute responding in a known and communicable way to a changing environmental condition, to a changing ecological process or function, or to a changing element of biodiversity (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Indigenous and local knowledge (ILK)

Indigenous and local knowledge (ILK) refers to dynamic bodies of integrated, holistic, social and ecological knowledge, practices and beliefs pertaining to the relationship of living beings, including people, with one another and with their environments (IPBES, 2021).

Indigenous Peoples' and Local Community Conserved Areas and Territories (ICCAs)

Indigenous Peoples' and Local Community Conserved Areas and Territories, referred to as ICCAs, are natural and/or modified ecosystems containing significant biodiversity values, ecological services and cultural values, voluntarily conserved by Indigenous peoples and local communities, both sedentary and mobile, through customary laws or other effective means. ICCAs can include ecosystems with

minimum to substantial human influence as well as cases of continuation, revival or modification of traditional practices or new initiatives taken up by communities in the face of new threats or opportunities. Several of them are inviolate zones ranging from very small to large stretches of land and waterscapes (ICCA Consortium, 2012).

Indigenous peoples and local communities (IPLCs)

The term “indigenous peoples and local communities” and its acronym “IPLC” are widely used by international organizations and conventions to refer to individuals and groups who self-identify as indigenous or as members of distinct local communities. We adopt this terminology in this assessment, with particular emphasis on those who “maintain an inter-generational historical connection to place and nature through livelihoods, cultural identity, languages, worldviews, institutions, and ecological knowledge” (see Chapter 1 and IPBES, 2020).

Indirect drivers

See “Drivers”.

Individual transferable quotas (ITQs)

A type of quota (a part of a Total Allowable Catch) allocated to individual fishermen or vessel owners and which can be sold to others (OECD, 2005).

Industrial fisheries or large-scale fisheries

Industrial fisheries are defined as a category of capture fishery that generally present (some of) the following characteristics: (i) high capital equipment and expenditure, (ii) highly level of mechanization, motorization and onboard processing, (iii) large vessel size (> 24 m and > 50 GT), (iv) based on a business more vertically integrated, with generally global market access, (v) operating offshore on a multi-days basis (see Chapter 1).

Institutions

Institutions are defined as encompassing all formal and informal interactions among stakeholders and social structures that determine how decisions are taken and implemented, how power is exercised, and how responsibilities are distributed (IPBES, 2019). This includes sets of rules, norms, values and procedures, which shape human interactions and with human interactions with nature (Brechin, 2003; McCay & Jentoft, 1996).

Institutional arrangements

Institutional arrangements can be seen as different (in)formal regimes and coalitions for collective action and inter-agent coordination, ranging from public-private cooperation and contracting schemes to organizational networking and policy arrangements (Geels, 2004; Klijn & Teisman, 2000).

Intellectual property rights

Intellectual property rights are the rights given to persons over the creations of their minds. They usually give the creator an exclusive right over the use of his/her creation for a certain period of time. Intellectual property rights are customarily divided into two main areas: rights related to copyright and industrial property (World Trade Organization, 2018).

Inter-generational equity

Inter-generational equity stipulates the rights and obligations of the current and future generations regarding the use of the environment. In the context of sustainable development, the Brundtland Report conceptualized it as “development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs” (IPBES, 2018).

Intra-generational equity

Intra-generational equity relates to notions of fairness and justice across the communities and states within the present generation. Inter-generational equity stipulates the rights and obligations of the current and future generations regarding the use of the environment. In the context of sustainable development, the Brundtland Report conceptualized it as “development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs” (IPBES, 2018).

Invasive alien species (IAS) / invasive species

Species whose introduction and/or spread by human action outside their natural distribution threaten biological diversity, food security, and human health and well-being. “Alien” refers to the species’ having been introduced outside its natural distribution (“exotic”, “non-native” and “non-indigenous” are synonyms for “alien”). “Invasive” means “tending to expand into and modify ecosystems to which it has been introduced”. Thus, a species may

be alien without being invasive, or, in the case of a species native to a region, it may increase and become invasive, without actually being an alien species (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

IPBES Conceptual Framework

The Platform’s conceptual framework has been designed to build shared understanding across disciplines, knowledge systems and stakeholders of the interplay between biodiversity and ecosystem drivers, and of the role they play in building a good quality of life through Nature’s contributions to people (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

IUCN Red list

The IUCN Red List is an indicator of the health of biodiversity. It provides taxonomic, conservation status and distribution information on plants, fungi and animals that have been globally evaluated using the IUCN Red List Categories and Criteria. This system is designed to determine the relative risk of extinction, and the main purpose of the IUCN Red List is to catalogue and highlight those plants and animals that are facing a higher risk of global extinction (IUCN, 2012b)

K

Keystone species

A species whose impact on the community or ecosystem is disproportionately large relative to its abundance. Effects can be produced by consumption (trophic interactions), competition, mutualism, dispersal, pollination, disease, or habitat modification (non-trophic interactions) (Millenium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005).

Knowledge System

A body of propositions that are adhered to, whether formally or informally, and are routinely used to claim truth. They are organized structures and dynamic processes (a) generating and representing content, components, classes, or types of knowledge, that are (b) domain-specific or characterized by domain-relevant features as defined by the user or consumer, (c) reinforced by a set of logical relationships that connect the content of knowledge to its value (utility), (d) enhanced by a set of iterative processes that enable the evolution, revision, adaptation, and advances, and (e) subject to criteria of relevance, reliability, and quality (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

L**Land cover**

The physical coverage of land, usually expressed in terms of vegetation cover or lack of it. Related to, but not synonymous with, land use (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005).

Land degradation

Refers to the many processes that drive the decline or loss in biodiversity, ecosystem functions or their benefits to people and includes the degradation of all terrestrial ecosystems. See ‘Habitat degradation’ (IPBES, 2019).

Land grabbing

See ‘Grabbing (of wild species and space)’.

Land use

The human use of a specific area for a certain purpose (such as residential; agriculture; recreation; industrial, etc.). Influenced by, but not synonymous with, land cover. Land use change refers to a change in the use or management of land by humans, which may lead to a change in land cover (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Landscape

An area of land that contains a mosaic of ecosystems, including human dominated ecosystems (IPBES, 2019).

Landscape heterogeneity

Landscape heterogeneity is a complex phenomenon involving the size, shape and composition of different landscape units and the spatial (and temporal) relations between them (G. Cale & J. Hobbs, 1994).

Large scale land acquisition (LSLA)

See ‘Grabbing (of wild species and space)’

Law of the Sea

The United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS), in force since 1994, defines the rights and obligations of nations (167 at present) with regard to the use of the world’s oceans and their resources, and the protection of the marine and coastal environment. The UNCLOS also defines national marine jurisdiction on maritime territories and provides guidelines related to the use and management of marine environment and resources (IPBES, 2019).

Legal and regulatory instruments

see “Policy instruments”.

Legal pluralism

Legal pluralism is a sensitizing concept for situations in which people draw upon several legal systems, irrespective of their status within the state legal system (Benda-Beckmann & Turner, 2018).

Learning (traditional and formal)

Learning refers to the process of knowledge and skills acquisition. Studies on learning have payed attention to the different ways people acquire knowledge, practices, and beliefs (i.e., imitation, copying, trial-and-error), but also to the dynamics of knowledge transmission, or the different sources from which knowledge, practices, and beliefs are passed from one individual to another (i.e., from parents, peers, teachers, prestigious peoples, media, etc.). Social learning is defined as the acquisition of new information by copying others, and it is a key human strategy that allows for the accumulation of culturally transmitted knowledge (Boyd & Richerson, 2005; Boyd & Silk, 2014).

Livelihood diversification

Livelihood diversification is defined as the process by which rural families construct a diverse portfolio of activities and social support capabilities in their struggle for survival and in order to improve their standards of living” (Ellis, 1998).

Living in harmony with nature

Within the context of the IPBES Conceptual Framework – a perspective on good quality of life based on the interdependence that exists among human beings, other living species and elements of nature. It implies that we should live peacefully alongside all other organisms even though we may need to exploit other organisms to some degree (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Local communities

Local communities” refers to non-indigenous communities with historical linkages to places and livelihoods characterized by long-term relationships with the natural environment, often over generations (see Chapter 1 and IPBES, 2020).

Local ecological knowledge (LEK)

Knowledge about nature, including organisms (animals and plants), ecosystems and ecological interactions, held by local people who interact with and use natural resources. This is a manifestation of indigenous local knowledge (ILK), but includes also knowledge held by those local

people who may not be officially recognized as indigenous (in legal terms). Like traditional ecological knowledge, LEK can be seen as a knowledge-practice-belief complex. In other words, it is a cumulative body of knowledge, practice, and belief, evolving by adaptive processes and handed down through generations by cultural transmission (Berkes, 2012). This encompasses ways of knowing and doing, which are dynamic concepts relying on building on experience and adapting to changes, thereby imbibe a strong learning-by-doing component (Berkes, 2015).

Local economies

Local economies and subsistence economies are defined as those that are small in scale and in which the use of resources (including wild species) are limited and exclusively used to meet local needs rather than accumulated or sold for profit (Emery & Pierce, 2005; Natcher, 2009; Schumann & Macinko, 2007).

Logging

Logging is defined as the removal of whole trees or woody parts of trees from their habitat. Logging generally results in the death of the tree, but also includes cases in which it may not, such as coppicing. Logging occurs in forests that may be classified as primary, naturally regenerating, planted, and plantation. This assessment does not address logging from plantation forests except as it has bearing on the practice in the other forest types. Harvest of non-woody parts of trees (e.g., leaves, propagules and bark) are here defined as gathering (see Chapter 1).

M**Malnutrition**

Malnutrition refers to deficiencies, excesses or imbalances in a person’s intake of energy and/or nutrients. The term malnutrition covers 2 broad groups of conditions. One is ‘undernutrition’ —which includes stunting (low height for age), wasting (low weight for height), underweight (low weight for age) and micronutrient deficiencies or insufficiencies (a lack of important vitamins and minerals). The other is overweight, obesity and diet-related noncommunicable diseases (such as heart disease, stroke, diabetes and cancer) (WHO, 2016).

Management of wild species

The management of wild species is the management process influencing

interactions among and between wild species, its habitats and humans to achieve predefined impacts valued by stakeholders. It attempts to balance the needs of wild species and the preservation of the ecosystems they inhabit with the needs of humans, using the best available sources of knowledge (Wikipedia, 2021).

Mangrove

Group of trees and shrubs that live in the coastal intertidal zone. Mangrove forests only grow at tropical and subtropical latitudes near the equator because they cannot withstand freezing temperatures (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Marginal lands

Land having limitations which in aggregate are severe for sustained application of a given use. On these lands, options are limited for diversification without the use of inputs; inappropriate management of lands may cause irreversible degradation (CGIAR, 1999).

Marginalization

Marginalisation is a complex and multidimensional concept, which simply cannot be seen as a state of being (e.g., a condition of low income or food insecurity) but needs to be considered a process over time with several inter-related elements interacting with social and economic conditions, political standing, and environmental health. A full understanding of the term marginalisation needs to be based on the view that the best judge of poverty and marginalisation are the people experiencing it (Nayak & Berkes, 2010).

Marginalized community

Marginalized communities, peoples or populations are groups and communities that experience discrimination and exclusion (social, political and economic) because of unequal power relationships across economic, political, social and cultural dimensions (National Collaborating Centre for Determinants of Health (Canada), 2021).

Mariculture

A branch of aquaculture involving the culture of organisms in a medium or environment which may be completely marine (sea), or sea water mixed to various degrees with fresh water, including brackish water areas (Sivalingam, 1981).

Megadiverse country

Countries (17) which have been identified as the most biodiversity-rich countries of the

world, with a particular focus on endemic biodiversity (UNEP-WCMC, 2014).

Meta-analysis

A quantitative statistical analysis of several separate but similar experiments or studies in order to test the pooled data for statistical significance (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Micronutrients

Substances that are only needed in very small amounts but essential to organisms to produce enzymes, hormones and other substances fundamental for proper growth and development (WHO, 2015).

Millennium Ecosystem Assessment

The Millennium Ecosystem Assessment is a major assessment of the human impact on the environment published in 2005 (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Mitigation

In the context of IPBES, an intervention to reduce negative or unsustainable uses of biodiversity and ecosystems (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Models

Qualitative or quantitative representations of key components of a system and of relationships between these components (IPBES, 2016c).

Monitoring

Monitoring is the repeated observation of a system in order to detect signs of change (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Mother Earth

An expression used in a number of countries and regions to refer to the planet Earth and the entity that sustains all living things found in nature with which humans have an indivisible, interdependent physical and spiritual relationship (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Multi-use system

Multi-use systems are defined as socio-ecosystems in which occur more than one use or practice (e.g., fishing and logging in mangroves) (see Chapter 4).

Multidisciplinary Expert Panel (MEP)

The IPBES Multidisciplinary Expert Panel is a subsidiary body established by the IPBES Plenary which oversees the scientific and technical functions of the Platform, a key role being to select experts to carry out assessments (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

N

Nagoya protocol

The Nagoya Protocol on Access to Genetic Resources and the Fair and Equitable Sharing of Benefits Arising from their Utilization (ABS) is a supplementary agreement to the 1992 Convention on Biological Diversity. It provides a transparent legal framework for the effective implementation of one of the three objectives of the CBD: the fair and equitable sharing of benefits arising out of the utilization of genetic resources, thereby contributing to the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity. The Nagoya Protocol aims to create greater legal certainty and transparency for both providers and users of genetic resources by establishing more predictable conditions for access to genetic resources and helping to ensure benefit-sharing when genetic resources leave the country providing the genetic resources. The Nagoya Protocol on ABS was adopted on 29 October 2010 in Nagoya, Japan and entered into force on 12 October 2014 (IPBES, 2019).

National biodiversity strategies and action plans (NBSAPs)

The Convention on Biological Diversity calls on each of its Parties to prepare a National Biodiversity Strategy and Action Plan (Article 6a) that establishes specific activities and targets for achieving the objectives of the Convention. These plans mostly are implemented by a partnership of conservation organizations. Species or habitats which are the subject of NBSAPs are the governments stated priorities for action and therefore raise greater concern where they are threatened. NBSAPs do not carry legal status and listed species and habitat types are not necessarily protected (although some are covered by other legislation) (Hesselink *et al.*, 2007).

Native species

Indigenous species of animals or plants that naturally occur in a given region or ecosystem (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Natural capital

A concept referring to the stock of renewable and non-renewable natural resources (e.g., plants, animals, air, water, soils, minerals) that combine to yield a flow of benefits to people (UNDP, 2016b). Within the IPBES conceptual framework, it is part of the "nature" category, representing an economic-utilitarian perspective on nature, specifically those aspects of nature that people use (or anticipate to use) as

source of Nature's contributions to people (IPBES, 2019).

Natural disaster

The effects of natural hazards, which are natural processes or phenomena occurring in the biosphere that may constitute a damaging event. Natural disasters can be for instance: earthquakes, floods, landslide, volcanic eruption, etc. (adapted from FAO, 2021).

Natural habitat

Areas composed of viable assemblages of plant and/or animal species of largely native origin and/or where human activity had not essentially modified an area's primary ecological functions and species composition (UNEP-WCMC, 2014).

Natural heritage

Natural features, geological and physiographical formations and delineated areas that constitute the habitat of threatened species of animals and plants and natural sites of outstanding universal value from the point of view of science, conservation or natural beauty (UNESCO, 1978).

Naturalized species

A species that, once it is introduced outside its native distributional range, establishes self-sustaining populations (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Nature

In the context of IPBES, refers to the natural world with an emphasis on its living components. Within the context of western science, it includes categories such as biodiversity, ecosystems (both structure and functioning), evolution, the biosphere; humankind's shared evolutionary heritage, and biocultural diversity. Within the context of other knowledge systems, it includes categories such as Mother Earth and systems of life, and it is often viewed as inextricably linked to humans, not as a separate entity (see "Mother Earth") (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Natural area or natural environment

Regions that have not been significantly altered by humankind. (Newsome *et al.*, 2013).

Nature-based recreation

Nature-based recreation may be defined as all forms of leisure that rely on the natural environment (Jacobs & Cottrell, 2015).

In the context of this assessment, it may involve extractive practices (i.e., fishing, gathering, terrestrial animal harvesting) or non-extractive practices (i.e., observing).

Nature-based solutions

Actions to protect, sustainably manage, and restore natural or modified ecosystems, that address societal challenges effectively and adaptively, simultaneously providing human well-being and biodiversity benefits (Cohen-Shacham *et al.*, 2016).

Nature-based tourism

Nature-based tourism is the activities of persons traveling to natural areas outside their usual environment for leisure and other purposes (based on UNWTO, glossary). In the context of this assessment, it may involve extractive practices (i.e., fishing, gathering, terrestrial animal harvesting) or non-extractive practices (i.e., observing).

Nature's Contributions to People (NCP)

Nature's contributions to people (NCP) are all the contributions, both positive and negative, of living nature (i.e., all organisms, ecosystems, and their associated ecological and evolutionary processes) to people's quality of life. Beneficial contributions include e.g., food provision, water purification, flood control, and artistic inspiration, whereas detrimental contributions include e.g., disease transmission and predation that damages people or their assets. NCP may be perceived as benefits or detriments depending on the cultural, temporal or spatial context (Díaz *et al.*, 2018).

IPBES considers a gradient of approaches to NCP, ranging from a purely generalizing approach to a purely context-specific one. Within the generalizing approach, IPBES identifies 18 categories of NCP, organized in three partially overlapping groups:

- Material contributions are substances, objects or other material elements from nature that directly sustain people's physical existence and material assets. They are typically physically consumed in the process of being experienced, for example when organisms are transformed into food, energy, or materials for clothing, shelter or ornamental purposes.
- Non-material contributions are nature's effects on subjective or psychological aspects underpinning people's quality of life, both individually and collectively. Examples include forests and coral reefs

providing opportunities for recreation and inspiration, or particular organism (animals, plants, fungi) or habitat (mountains, lakes) being the basis of spiritual or social-cohesion experiences.

- Regulating contributions are functional and structural aspects of organisms and ecosystems that modify environmental conditions experienced by people, and/or regulate the generation of material and non-material contributions. Regulating contributions frequently affect quality of life in indirect ways. For example, people directly enjoy useful or beautiful plants, but only indirectly the soil organisms that are essential for the supply of nutrients to such plants. (IPBES, 2019).

Nexus

A perspective which emphasizes the inter-relatedness and interdependencies of ecosystem components and human uses, and their dynamics and fluxes across spatial scales and between compartments. Instead of just looking at individual components, the functioning, productivity and management of a complex system is taken into consideration. In such complex systems there are trade-offs as well as facilitation and amplification between the different components. A nexus approach can help address synergies and trade-offs among multiple sectors and among various Sustainable Development Goals and biodiversity targets simultaneously (adapted from (UNU-FLORES, 2018).

Niche (ecological)

A species' position within an ecosystem. This definition includes both the abiotic and biotic conditions necessary for the species to be able to persist (e.g., temperature range, food sources) and its ecological role, function or "job" (Polechová & Storch, 2019).

Nitrogen deposition

The nitrogen transferred from the atmosphere to the Earth's surface by the processes of wet deposition and dry deposition (IPCC, 2014).

Nitrogen-fixing species

Plants, such as legumes, living in symbiosis with micro-organisms in their roots that can perform biological nitrogen fixation, i.e., convert atmospheric nitrogen (N₂) to ammonia (NH₃). Plants can then assimilate NH₃ to produce biomolecules (Wagner, 2011).

Non-Indigenous Species or Non-native species or Alien species

See “Invasive alien species”.

Non-extractive practices

Non-extractive practices are defined as practices based on the observation of wild species in a way that does not involve the harvest or removal of any part of the organism. The observation can imply some interaction with the wild species, such as the activities of wildlife and whale watching or no interaction with the wild species, such as remote photography (see Chapter 1).

Non-lethal harvest

Non-lethal harvest is defined as the temporary or permanent capture of live animals from their habitat without mortality, such as for the aquarium trade, pet trade or zoos, tag and release activities. Non-lethal harvest of animals also includes the parts or products of animals that do not lead to the mortality of the host, such as vicuna fiber, swift nests or wild honey (see Chapter 1).

Nutrient cycling

The processes by which elements are extracted from their mineral, aquatic, or atmospheric sources or recycled from their organic forms, converting them to the ionic form in which biotic uptake occurs and ultimately returning them to the atmosphere, water, or soil (Millenium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005).

O**Observing**

Observing is defined as a non-extractive practice that is based on the observation of wild species. The observation can imply some interaction with the wild species, such as the activities of wildlife tourism and whale watching or no interaction with the wild species, such as photography (see Chapter 1).

Ocean acidification

A reduction in the pH of the ocean over an extended period, typically decades or longer, which is caused primarily by uptake of carbon dioxide from the atmosphere, but can also be caused by other chemical additions or subtractions from the ocean. Anthropogenic ocean acidification refers to the component of pH reduction that is caused by human activity (IPCC, 2014).

Oligotrophic

Nutrient-poor environment (IUCN, 2012a).

Overexploitation

Overexploitation means harvesting species from the wild at rates faster than natural populations can recover. Includes overfishing, and overgrazing (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Overgrazing

Overgrazing occurs when plants are exposed to intensive grazing for extended periods of time, or without sufficient recovery periods. It can be caused by either livestock in poorly managed agricultural applications, game reserves, or nature reserves. It can also be caused by immobile, travel restricted populations of native or non-native wild animals (IPBES, 2018).

P**Participatory methods**

Participatory research methods are a variety of qualitative and quantitative methods “geared towards planning and conducting the research process with those people whose life-world and meaningful actions are under study” (Bergold & Thomas, 2012). Participatory methods acknowledge the possibility, the significance, and the usefulness of involving research partners in the knowledge-production process (Bergold, 2007).

Participatory process

Specific methods employed to achieve active participation by all members of a group in a decision-making process (Chatty *et al.*, 2003).

Participatory governance

A variant or subset of governance which puts emphasis on democratic engagement, in particular through deliberative practices (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Pathways

In the context of the IPBES global assessment, trajectories toward the achievement of goals and targets for biodiversity conservation and management of nature and Nature’s contributions to people (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Payment for ecosystem services (PES)

Payments for Ecosystem Services (PES) are a specific class of approach, used to facilitate voluntary transaction between a provider and a user of a service, conditioned on natural resource management rules for dealing with environmental externalities (Wunder, 2015). PES is created to deal with

market failures, environmental externalities, property rights problems and asymmetric information between economic actors.

Peatlands

Wetlands which accumulate organic plant matter *in situ* because waterlogging prevents aerobic decomposition and the much slower rate of the resulting anaerobic decay is exceeded by the rate of accumulation (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Pelagic

Occurring or living in open waters or near the surface with little contact with or dependency on the bottom (IUCN, 2012a).

Persistent organic pollutants (POPs)

Organic compounds that are resistant to environmental degradation through chemical, biological, and photolytic processes. POPs persist in the environment for long periods, are capable of long-range transport, bioaccumulate in human and animal tissue and biomagnify in food chains, and have potentially significant impacts on human health and the environment. Exposure to POPs can cause serious health problems including certain cancers, birth defects, dysfunctional immune and reproductive systems, greater susceptibility to disease and even diminished intelligence (Stockholm Convention Secretariat, 2017).

Phenology

The study of the relationship between climate and the timing of periodic natural phenomena such as migration of birds, bud bursting, or flowering of plants (IUCN, 2012a).

Phenotype

The characteristics of an individual resulting from interaction between its genotype (genetic constitution) and its environment (IUCN, 2012a). These characteristics often include behavior, physiology (e.g., oxygen consumption, heart rate), life history (e.g., body size, age, offspring number), or morphology (e.g., body proportions).

Phenotypic attributes (biodiversity)

A distinct variant of a phenotypic characteristic of an organism; it may be either inherited or determined environmentally, but typically occurs as a combination of the two (Lawrence, 2005).

Phylogenetic diversity

Although species richness is a commonly used measure of biodiversity, it fails to capture the reality that species without

close relatives contribute more uniqueness than do species with many close relatives. Phylogenetic diversity is used as a general term for a range of measures that consider the total length of all the branches linking a set of species on their phylogeny (“evolutionary tree”) and so reflect species’ evolutionary uniqueness. One of the first such measures (Faith, 1992) is simply the sum of the branch lengths.

Plankton

Aquatic organisms that drift or swim weakly. Phytoplankton are the plant forms of plankton (e.g., diatoms), and are the dominant plants in the sea. Zooplankton are the animal forms of plankton. Picoplankton are all forms of plankton which size is comprised between 0.2 and 2 micrometers (mostly bacteria) (Mullin, 2001).

Plenary

Within the context of IPBES – the decision-making body comprising all of the members of IPBES (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Poaching

Poaching is defined as the illegal removal of wild species from a place where such practices are specially reserved or forbidden.

Policy instrument

Policy instruments can be defined as “the set of techniques by which governmental authorities wield their power in attempting to ensure support and effect or prevent social change (Vedung, 2017). In this assessment, the following four categories of policy instruments are identified:

- **Legal and regulatory instruments:** legal and regulatory instruments include legislation, standards, regulations, rules, agreements, planning and so on.
- **Economic and financial instruments:** economic and financial instruments include traditional fiscal instruments, including for example taxes (and tax reliefs), subsidies and charges and conditional and voluntary incentive scheme such as payment for environmental services (PES). What we term economic and financial instruments are any policy options that use prices as a basis for the governance of wild species.
- **Social and Instruments:** Social and information-based instruments include community-based instruments,

education/training, counselling, certification schemes, ecolabels, corporate social responsibility, and so on

- **Rights-Based and Customary**

Instruments: Right-based instruments include human rights, customary norms and traditional knowledge. The unwritten, negotiable and relational nature of customary law is an important determinant for programming, as is the variety in normative beliefs and practices within customary communities. Customary norms are formulated, renegotiated and flexibly applied in administrative structures and dispute settlement institutions. (IPBES, 2021)

Policy options

(for the use of wild species)

Policy options are defined as potential policies in terms of their ability to achieve the stated policy goals. Chapter 6 present the range of policy options available to support the sustainable use of wild species, at a range of spatial scales (local, national, international), and across five key practices (fishing, gathering, terrestrial animal harvesting, logging, and non-extractive practices). Four groups of policy instruments are explored: i) legal and regulatory, ii) economic and financial, iii) social and information based, and iv) rights-based and customary instruments (see Chapter 6, section 6.4).

Policy Support Tools

Approaches and techniques based on science and other knowledge systems that can inform, assist and enhance relevant decisions, policy making and implementation at local, national, regional and global levels to protect nature, thereby promoting Nature’s contributions to people and a good quality of life (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Pollination

The transfer of pollen from an anther to a stigma. Pollination may occur within flowers of the same plant, between flowers of the same plant, or between flowers of different plants (or combinations thereof) (IPBES, 2016a).

Pollution

Pollution is the introduction of contaminants into the natural environment that cause adverse change (IPBES, 2018).

Polycentric governance

An organizational structure where multiple

independent actors mutually order their relationships with one another under a general system of rules (Ostrom, 2010).

Poverty

Poverty is a pronounced deprivation of well-being related to lacking the means of material subsistence. Its manifestations include hunger and malnutrition, limited access to education and other basic services. Other corollaries of poverty are social discrimination and exclusion as well as the lack of participation in decision-making (adapted from (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Practices (type of wild species practices)

See “gathering”, “fishing”, “terrestrial animal harvesting”, “logging”, “non-extractive practices” and “non-lethal harvest”.

Primary production

The conversion of energy to organic substances by photosynthetic and chemosynthetic autotrophic organisms (IPBES, 2018).

Prior informed consent (PIC)

See “Free, prior and informed consent (FPIC)”.

Precautionary principle

Pertains to risk management and states that if an action or policy has a suspected risk of causing harm to the public or to the environment, in the absence of scientific consensus that the action or policy is not harmful, the burden of proof that it is not harmful falls on those taking an action. The principle is used to justify discretionary decisions when the possibility of harm from making a certain decision (e.g., taking a particular course of action) is not, or has not been, established through extensive scientific knowledge. The principle implies that there is a social responsibility to protect the public from exposure to harm, when scientific investigation has found a plausible risk or if a potential plausible risk has been identified (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Protected area

A protected area is a clearly defined geographical space, recognized, dedicated and managed, through legal or other effective means, to achieve the long-term conservation of nature with associated ecosystem services and cultural values (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Provisioning services

The products people obtain from ecosystems; may include food, freshwater, timber, fibers, medicinal plants (IPBES, 2018).

R**Ramsar Convention on Wetlands**

The Convention on Wetlands, called the Ramsar Convention, of International Importance especially as Waterfowl Habitat, is an intergovernmental treaty that provides the framework for national action and international cooperation for the conservation and wise use of wetlands and their resources (IPBES, 2018).

Ramsar site(s)

A Ramsar site is a wetland site designated of international importance especially as Waterfowl Habitat under the Ramsar Convention, an intergovernmental environment treaty established in 1975 by UNESCO, coming into force in 1975. Ramsar site refers to wetland of international significance in terms of ecology, botany, zoology, limnology or hydrology. Such site meets at least one of the criteria of Identifying Wetlands of International Importance set by Ramsar Convention and is designated by appropriate national authority to be added to Ramsar list (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Rangeland

Natural grasslands used for livestock grazing (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Rebound effect

The pattern by which resource users tend to compensate for improved efficiency by shifting behavior towards greater consumption, which undermines apparent gains. For example, an increased fuel saving of motor vehicle tends to be compensated by spending more money on other resources or by driving more (Alcott, 2005).

Recreational uses (of wild species)

Recreational uses are defined as uses of wild species in which enjoyment is considered a primary value.

Recruitment

The influx of new members into a population by reproduction or immigration (IUCN, 2012a).

Reduced impact logging (RIL)

The intensively planned and carefully controlled implementation of timber harvesting operations to minimize the

environmental impact on forest stands and soils (FAO, 2021).

Reducing emissions from deforestation and forest degradation (REDD+)

Mechanism developed by Parties to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC). It creates a financial value for the carbon stored in forests by offering incentives for developing countries to reduce emissions from forested lands and invest in low-carbon paths to sustainable development. Developing countries would receive results-based payments for results-based actions. REDD+ goes beyond simply deforestation and forest degradation, and includes the role of conservation, sustainable management of forests and enhancement of forest carbon stocks (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Reforestation

Planting of forests on lands that have previously contained forests but that have been converted to some other use (IPCC, 2014).

Regime

A long-term qualitative behavior where the system's dynamics tend to stabilize, at different spatial and temporal scales in marine, terrestrial and polar systems (Rocha *et al.*, 2015).

Regime shift

Substantial reorganization in system structure, functions and feedbacks that often occurs abruptly and persists over time (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Rehabilitation

Rehabilitation refers to restoration activities that move a site towards a natural state baseline in a limited number of components (i.e., soil, water, and/or biodiversity), including natural regeneration, conservation agriculture, and emergent ecosystems (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Relational value

See "Values".

Remote sensing

Methods for gathering data on a large or landscape scale which do not involve on-the ground measurement, especially satellite photographs and aerial photographs; often used in conjunction with Geographic Information Systems (IUCN, 2012a).

Resilience

The capacity of a system to absorb disturbance and reorganize while undergoing change so as to still retain essentially the same function, structure, identity, and feedbacks (B. Walker *et al.*, 2004).

Resolution (spatial or temporal)

See "scales"

Restoration

Any intentional activities that initiate or accelerate the recovery of an ecosystem from a degraded state (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Richness (biodiversity)

The number of biological entities (species, genotypes, etc.) within a given sample. Sometimes used as synonym of species diversity (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Rights-Based and Customary Instruments

See "Policy instruments".

Ritual uses (of wild species)

See "Ceremonial uses"

Roundwood (industrial)

Industrial round wood is defined as all roundwood used for any purpose other than energy. It comprises pulpwood, sawlogs and veneer logs (see Chapter 3).

Rules and regulations

Set of rules to govern the work and decision making of its formal settings (United Nations Environment Programme & United Nations Environment Programme, 2007).

Rural development

Rural development is the process of improving the opportunities and well-being of rural people. It is a process of change in the characteristics of rural societies. In addition to agricultural development, it involves human development and social and environment objectives, as opposed to just economic ones. Therefore, rural development encompasses health, education, and other social services. It also uses a multisector approach for promoting agriculture, extracting minerals, tourism, recreation, and niche manufacturing (IFAD, 2004).

S**Sacred groves**

A particular type of sacred natural sites represented by patches of forest revered

as sacred (Bhagwat & Rutte, 2006). Sacred groves may be revered e.g., as burial grounds (Mgumia & Oba, 2003) or sites of ancestral or deity worship (Ramakrishnan *et al.*, 1998). There are locally-established rules that regulate how sacred groves can be used (Hughes & Chandran, 1998). Observation of those rules often contributes to the biodiversity conservation on those sites (Bhagwat & Rutte, 2006).

Sacred natural sites

Areas of land or water that have special spiritual significance to peoples and communities (Verschuuren *et al.*, 2010). They consist of natural features, ranging from entire ecosystems, such as mountains, forests or islands, to single natural features such as a tree, spring or boulder, and are very important for the conservation of nature and culture. Sacred natural sites have been managed based on indigenous and local knowledge systems, developed over long periods of time, and are source of cultural identity.

Savanna

Biome characterized by a continuous layer of herbaceous plants, mostly grasses, and a discontinuous upper layer of trees that may vary in density (modified from IPBES, core glossary).

Sawnwood

Sawnwood is defined as planks, sleepers (cross-ties), beams, joists, boards, rafters, 1679 scantlings, laths, boxboards and lumber that exceed 5 mm in thickness (see Chapter 3).

Scale

Definitions of scale abound. For purposes of this assessment, scale is defined as the spatial or temporal extent of an object, event, or phenomenon and/or the unit of measure used in its analysis.

The temporal scale is comprised of two properties:

- temporal extent – the total length of the time period of interest for a particular study (e.g., 10 years, 50 years, or 100 years);
- temporal grain (or resolution) – the temporal frequency with which data are observed or projected within this total period (e.g., at 1-year, 5-year or 10-year intervals).

The spatial scale is comprised of two properties:

- spatial extent – the size of the total area of interest for a particular study (e.g., a watershed, a country, the entire planet);
- spatial grain (or resolution) – the size of the spatial units within this total area for which data are observed or predicted (e.g., fine-grained or coarse-grained grid cells) (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Scenarios

Representations of possible futures for one or more components of a system, particularly, in this assessment, for drivers of change in nature and nature's benefits, including alternative policy or management options.

- Exploratory scenarios (also known as “explorative scenarios” or “descriptive scenarios”) are scenarios that examine a range of plausible futures, based on potential trajectories of drivers – either indirect (e.g., socio-political, economic and technological factors) or direct (e.g., habitat conversion, climate change).
- Target-seeking scenarios (also known as “goal-seeking scenarios” or “normative scenarios”) are scenarios that start with the definition of a clear objective, or a set of objectives, specified either in terms of achievable targets, or as an objective function to be optimized, and then identify different pathways to achieving this outcome (e.g., through backcasting).
- Intervention scenarios are scenarios that evaluate alternative policy or management options – either through target seeking (also known as “goal seeking” or “normative scenario analysis”) or through policy screening (also known as “ex-ante assessment”).
- Policy-evaluation scenarios are scenarios, including counterfactual scenarios, used in ex-post assessments of the gap between policy objectives and actual policy results, as part of the policy-review phase of the policy cycle.
- Policy-screening scenarios are scenarios used in ex-ante assessments, to forecast the effects of alternative policy or management options (interventions) on environmental outcomes (IPBES, 2016b; IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Sea ice

Any form of ice found at sea which has originated from the freezing of sea water (sea ice does not include superstructure icing). Ice formed from the freezing of the waters of the Great Lakes will be considered the same as sea ice (NOAA's National Weather Service, 2009).

Seascape

Seascape can be defined as a spatially heterogeneous area of coastal environment (i.e., intertidal, brackish) that can be perceived as a mosaic of patches, a spatial gradient, or some other geometric patterning. The tropical coastal “seascape” often includes a patchwork of mangroves, seagrass beds, and coral reefs that produces a variety of natural resources and ecosystem services (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Sector

A distinct part of society, or of a nation's economy (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Second-growth forest

Regenerating forest after disturbance, such as fire or clear-cutting (IUCN, 2012a).

Selective hunting

Selective hunting, in this assessment, refers to situations where hunters focus on particular species, or on individual animals within a population that have particular attributes, e.g., large size, large horns or antlers.

Semi-natural ecosystems

An ecosystem with most of its processes and biodiversity intact, though altered by human activity in strength or abundance relative to the natural state (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Sense of place

Characteristics that make a place special or unique, as well as to those that foster a sense of authentic human attachment and belonging (Casey, 2001).

Shamanism

A system that links people to the vital forces of nature, especially the soul or inner-self of non-humans or nature spirits, through the mediation of a specialist, the shaman. Shamans are generally trained through enduring experiences including the consumption of psychotropic substances that lead them to experience spiritual connections that are mobilized to combat

illness and any dangers that may affect their community (IPBES, 2019).

Shared socio-economic pathways (SPPs)

Shared Socio-economic Pathways (SSPs) describe alternative socioeconomic futures in the absence of climate policy intervention, comprising sustainable development (SSP1), regional rivalry (SSP3), inequality (SSP4), fossil-fuelled development (SSP5) and middle-of-the-road development (SSP2). The combination of SSP-based socio-economic scenarios and Representative Concentration Pathway (RCP)-based climate projections provides an integrative frame for climate impact and policy analysis (IPCC, 2018).

Shifting cultivation

An agricultural system in which plots of land are cultivated temporarily, then abandoned to regenerate soil fertility by the regeneration of natural vegetation. The system involves 1) the removal of the natural vegetation (usually forest or shrub land) in most cases (though not exclusively) by cutting and subsequent burning, mulching, or their combinations (such as in slash-and-burn, slash-and-mulch); 2) an alternation between a short duration of cultivation and a comparatively long duration of bush or forest fallow (such as in swidden agroforestry); and 3) the regular, in most cases cyclical, shifting of field (Erni, 2015). Shifting cultivation systems are found around the world, particularly in tropical areas, in a wide range of soils and vegetation types, under a diversity of land and resource management, using different crops and cultivation methods, and are practiced by innumerable Indigenous Peoples and Local Communities (Heinimann *et al.*, 2017; Nye & Greenland, 1960).

Silviculture

The art and science of controlling the establishment, growth, composition, health and quality of forest and woodlands to meet the targeted diverse needs and values of landowners and society on a sustainable basis (FAO, 2006).

Slash-and-burn agriculture

See 'Shifting cultivation'.

Small-scale or non-industrial fisheries

Small-scale fisheries are defined as a category of capture fishery that generally present (some of) the following characteristics: (i) low capital investment, (ii) high labor activities often family or

community-based, (iii) no vessel or small size vessel (< 12m and < 10 GT), (iv) relatively low production, which is household consumed or locally and directly sold and (v) operating close to the shoreline on a single day basis (see Chapter 1).

Social capital

As used in the global assessment, social capital refers to networks together with shared norms, values and understandings that facilitate co-operation within or among groups. Put together, these networks and understandings engender trust and so enable people to work together (OECD, 2007b).

Social norms

A social norm is what people in some group believe to be normal in the group, that is, believed to be a typical action, an appropriate action, or both (Gerry Mackie *et al.*, 2015).

Social and cultural based Instruments

see "Policy instruments".

Social safety net

Social welfare services provided by a community of individuals at the state and local levels. These services are geared toward eliminating poverty in a specific area. These services may include housing re-assignment, job placement, subsidies for household bills, and other cash equivalents for food. Social safety net works in conjunction with a number of other poverty reduction programs with the primary goal of reducing/preventing poverty (UNESCWA, 2015).

Social welfare

The condition of a society emphasizing happiness and contentment; social welfare relates to how individuals use their relationships to other actors in societies for their own and for the collective good; it has both material elements and wider spiritual and social dimensions (Adger, 2003).

Socio-ecological production landscapes and seascapes (SEPLS)

Dynamic mosaics of habitats and land uses where the harmonious interaction between people and nature maintains biodiversity while providing humans with the goods and services needed for their livelihoods, survival and well-being in a sustainable manner (IPSI, 2018).

Social-ecological or Socio-ecological system

Social-ecological systems are complex adaptive systems in which people and nature are inextricably linked, in which both the social and ecological components exert strong influence over outcomes. The social dimension includes actors, institutions, cultures and economies, including livelihoods. The ecological dimension includes wild species and the ecosystem they inhabit.

Soil fertility

The capacity of a soil to receive, store and transmit energy to support plant growth. It is the component of overall soil productivity that deals with its available nutrient status, and its ability to provide nutrients out of its own reserves and through external applications for crop production (FAO, 2018b).

Soil organic matter (SOM)

Matter consisting of plant and/or animal organic materials, and the conversion products of those materials in soils (FAO & ITPS, 2015).

Soil quality

Soil quality is a measure of the soil's ability to provide ecosystem and social services through its capacities to perform its functions under changing conditions. Soil quality reflects how well a soil performs the functions of maintaining biodiversity and productivity, partitioning water and solute flow, filtering and buffering, nutrient cycling, and providing support for plants and other structures (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Species

An interbreeding group of organisms that is reproductively isolated from all other organisms, although there are many partial exceptions to this rule in particular taxa. Operationally, the term species is a generally agreed fundamental taxonomic unit, based on morphological or genetic similarity that once described and accepted is associated with a unique scientific name (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005).

Species composition

The array of species in a specific sample, community, or area (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Species distribution models

Species distribution models relate field observations of the presence/absence of a species to environmental predictor variables,

based on statistically or theoretically derived response surfaces, for prediction and inference. The predictor variables are often climatic but can include other environmental variables (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Species richness

The number of species within a given sample, community, or area (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Species traits

The morphological, physiological, phonological or behavioral characteristics of an organism, that typically inform about its response to the environment and effects on the ecosystem (Lavorel & Garnier, 2002; Violle *et al.*, 2007).

Spillover effects

Human impacts or natural disturbances beyond system boundaries. These effects can be positive or negative, socioeconomic or/and environmental and can be much more profound than the effects within the focal system (Liu *et al.*, 2013).

Stability (socio-ecological system)

The degree to which a system can continue to function if inputs, controls, or conditions are disrupted. It is a reflection of how minor a perturbation is capable of rendering the system inoperable or degraded; the types of perturbation to which the system is especially vulnerable; whether the system can “ignore” certain stresses; and the degree to which the system can be altered by surprise (Kerner & Thomas, 2014).

Stakeholders

Any individuals, groups or organizations who affect, or could be affected (whether positively or negatively) by a particular issue and its associated policies, decisions and action (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

State (socio-ecological system)

The collection of variables that describe the whole of the social–ecological system, including the attributes of ecosystem service providers and beneficiaries (Harrington *et al.*, 2010).

Status

Based in actual observations (data) (IPBES, 2016c)

Stewardship practices

The responsible use and protection of the natural environment through conservation actions, active restoration and the

sustainable use and management of resources (Bennett *et al.*, 2018).

Subsistence

Subsistence is defined as the livelihood uses in which a species is used or consumed directly by the individual who obtained it from the wild and his/her/their direct social network (see Chapter 1).

Succession (ecological)

The process whereby communities of plants, animals and microorganisms are replaced by others, usually more complex, over time as an area is colonized. Primary succession occurs on bare ground (e.g., after a volcanic eruption); secondary succession follows the interruption of a primary succession, e.g., after disturbances such as logging, ploughing or burning (Lawrence, 2005).

Summary for Policy-makers

A component of any report, providing a policy-relevant but not policy prescriptive summary of that report (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Sustainable development

Development that meets the needs and aspirations of the current generation without compromising the ability to meet those of future generations (Hesselink *et al.*, 2007).

Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

A set of goals adopted by the United Nations on September 25, 2015 to end poverty, protect the planet, and ensure prosperity for all as part of a new sustainable development agenda. Each goal has specific targets to be achieved over the next 15 years (IPBES, 2018).

Sustainable livelihood

Sustainable livelihoods is defined as the ability of the users to cope with and respond to the stresses and shocks related to fluctuations in the Nature’s contribution to people that adversely impact their material, relational and subjective dimensions of life and create vulnerabilities, develop their capabilities to strengthen access and entitlements to the variety of livelihood resources, without unnecessarily undermining the natural resource base (the wild species and its natural environment), so as to achieve a desirable standard of living that befits them as humans and also approved by the measures of wellbeing and human development (Allison & Horemans, 2006; Chambers & Conway, 1992).

Sustainable use

Sustainable use is defined by the Convention on Biological Diversity since 1992 as “the use of components of biological diversity in a way and at a rate that does not lead to the long-term decline of biological diversity, thereby maintaining its potential to meet the needs and aspirations of present and future generations.” This assessment notes that sustainable use is also an outcome of social-ecological systems that aim to maintain biodiversity and ecosystem functions in the long term, while contributing to human well-being. It is a dynamic process as wild species, the ecosystems that support them and the social systems within which uses occur, change over time and space.

This assessment notes the social, economic, and environmental dimensions of sustainability as identified by the 2030 Agenda for sustainable development and its Sustainable Development Goals.

Synergies

The interaction or cooperation of two or more agents to produce a combined effect greater than the sum of their separate effects (IPBES, 2018).

Synthetic biology

Adopted as a working definition by the Convention on Biological Diversity AHTEG on Synthetic Biology, Synthetic biology was defined as “a further development and new dimension of modern biotechnology that combines science, technology, and engineering to facilitate and accelerate the understanding, design, redesign, manufacture and/or modification of genetic materials, living organisms and biological systems” (CBD, 2016).

Systematic review

Collation and critical analysis of multiple research studies or papers, using a structured methodology (IPBES, 2018).

T

Taboo

A social or religious custom prohibiting or restricting a particular practice or forbidding association with a particular person, place, or behavior (IPBES, 2019).

Target-seeking scenarios

See “scenarios”

Taxon/Taxonomic group

A category applied to a group in a formal system of nomenclature, e.g., species, genus, family etc. (plural: taxa) (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Telecoupling

Socioeconomic-environmental interactions over distances (Liu *et al.*, 2013). It is an umbrella concept that encompasses various types of distant interactions, such as international trade, tourism, migration, foreign investment, species invasion, payments for ecosystem services, water transfer, information dissemination, knowledge transfer, and technology transfer (Liu *et al.*, 2015).

Temporal Scales

Measurements or other observations reported along a time series (IPBES, 2018).

Tenure

Tenure systems define who can use which Nature's contributions to people, for how long and under what conditions.

Three related aspects of tenure offer a comprehensive understanding of the term. They include (1) tenure as a set of rights, (2) key responsibilities in relation to tenure, and (3) enabling conditions that facilitate governance of tenure. From this combined perspective, tenure is understood as the combination of a set of specific rights that connect the resource users with various aspects of the resource and puts the control and decision-making power in their hands. These rights span social, ecological, economic, and political aspects of tenure, and help provide directions to moving toward effective governance. Rights are connected with responsibilities that range from the duties of the users to maintain the resource to the duties to be performed by the state, and those jointly by both. The exercise of tenure rights can only be possible if certain conditions are meaningfully met because they offer the much required social, ecological, and political environment for the operationalization of tenure rights, performance of the tenure related duties, and necessary security and protection against tenure violations.

From an integrated social-ecological (human-environmental) systems perspective, tenure is defined as relationships (also interactions and connections) between people (the users) who seek tenure and between the people (users) and the environment (includes the resource)

to which tenure is being sought. Governance of tenure is then about the manner in which these host of relationships, interactions, and connections are addressed and promoted. Tenure in the context of sustainable use of wild species is not a static concept and, therefore, can be best understood as a process and its governance as continuous (Díaz *et al.*, 2018; FAO, 2015; IPBES core glossary, 2021; Nayak, 2017).

Tenure security

An agreement between an individual or group to land and residential property, which is governed and regulated by a legal and administrative framework includes both customary and statutory systems (Payne & Durand-Lasserve, 2012).

Terrestrial animal harvesting

Terrestrial animal harvesting is defined as the removal from their habitat of animals (vertebrates and invertebrates) that spend some or all of their life cycle in terrestrial environments. As for fishing, terrestrial animal harvesting often results in the death of the animal, but it may not in some cases. To reflect both situations, terrestrial animal harvesting has been sub-divided into a lethal and a "non-lethal" category. Hunting is defined as the lethal category of terrestrial animal harvesting which leads to the killing of the animal, such as in trophy hunting. "Non-lethal" terrestrial animal harvesting is defined as the temporary or permanent capture of live animals from their habitat without intended mortality, such as pet trade, falconry or green hunting. Non-lethal harvest of animals also includes removal of parts or products of animals that do not lead to the mortality of the host, such as vicuña fiber or wild honey. Unintended mortality may however occur in this category and the term "non-lethal" is therefore put in quotes. (see Chapter 1).

Territorial use rights in fisheries (TURFs)

The restriction of access to, and use of, a particular fishing ground or site to a small group or an individual. This group can determine how to harvest fish from the site and to whom the fish is allocated (Ward *et al.*, 2004).

Threatened species

In the IUCN Red List terminology, a threatened species is any species listed in the Red List categories Critically Endangered, Endangered, or Vulnerable (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Threshold effect

Harmful or fatal effect of a small change in environmental conditions that exceeds the limit of tolerance of an organism or population of a species (Miller & Spoolman, 2009).

Tipping point

A set of conditions of an ecological or social system where further perturbation will cause rapid change and prevent the system from returning to its former state (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Total allowable catch (TAC)

The total catch allowed to be taken from a resource within a specified time period (usually a year) by all operators; designated by the regulatory authority. Usually allocated in the form of quotas (IUCN, 2012a).

Totemism

A principle or an ontology found within societies that differentiate different sections of the society, according to the attachment of these sections to animal or plant tutelary spirits. In other words, totemism defines discontinuities in social order according to each group's attachment to a specific animal or plant spirit that is perceived as having similar features to this section (or clan) and an inner-self that also resembles people in this section (and reciprocally) (IPBES, 2019).

Trade (formal or informal)

Trade is defined in formal markets as the exchanges in which records are kept and statistics generated. It is expected that currency is the medium of exchange in formal markets. Trade in informal markets encompasses exchanges in which neither records nor statistics are generated; the medium of exchange may be currency or goods and/or services (see Chapter 1).

Trade-off

A trade-off is a situation where an improvement in the status of one aspect of the environment or of human well-being is necessarily associated with a decline in or loss of a different aspect. Trade-offs characterize most complex systems, and are important to consider when making decisions that aim to improve environmental and/or socio-economic outcomes. Trade-offs are distinct from synergies (the latter are also referred to as "win-win" scenarios): synergies arise when the enhancement of one desirable outcome leads to enhancement of another (IPBES, 2019).

Traditional and community-based management systems

Resource management strategies and practices based on accumulated indigenous and local knowledge acquired through community-based learning processes and transmitted between successive generations (IPBES, 2019).

Traditional Knowledge (TK)

The concept of Traditional Knowledge (TK) in the Convention for Biological Diversity (CBD) has two characteristics. Firstly, CBD defines TK as one kind of knowledge, innovations and practices which is helpful to conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity. Secondly, CBD limits the TK to link with indigenous peoples and local communities (IPLCs) embodying traditional lifestyles, i.e., these TK were created and preserved by IPLCs and they are accumulated, developed and inherited generation by generation (IPBES, 2018).

Traditional Ecological Knowledge (TEK)

Traditional Ecological Knowledge (TEK) is a cumulative body of knowledge and beliefs, handed down through generations by cultural transmission, about the relationship of living beings (including humans) with one another and with their environment. Further, TEK is an attribute of societies with historical continuity in resource use practices; by and large, there are non-industrial or less technologically advanced societies, many of them indigenous or tribal (Berkes, 1993).

Traditional medicinal practice

Traditional medicine is the sum total of the knowledge, skill, and practices based on the theories, beliefs, and experiences indigenous to different cultures, whether explicable or not, used in the maintenance of health as well as in the prevention, diagnosis, improvement or treatment of physical and mental illness (WHO, 2008, 2013).

Transboundary

Flows, interactions, relationships across boundary, in reference to jurisdictions, political units, physical nature features (IPBES, 2018).

Transformative change

Transformative change is defined in line with previous work of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services approved by its Plenary, as a fundamental, system-wide reorganization across technological,

economic and social factors, including paradigms, goals and values (IPBES, 2019), needed for the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity, good quality of life and sustainable development.

Trends

The general direction in which the structure or dynamics of a system tends to change, even if individual observations vary (IPBES, 2016c).

Trophic cascades

The chain of knock – on extinctions observed or predicted to occur following the loss of one or a few species that play a critical role (e.g., as a pollinator) in ecosystem functioning (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Trophic level

The level in the food chain in which one group of organisms serves as a source of nutrition for another group of organisms (e.g., primary producers, primary or secondary consumers, decomposers) (IPBES, 2019).

Trophy hunting

Trophy hunting is defined as the hunting for one or more individuals of a particular species with specific desired characteristics (such as large size or antlers) with the payment of a fee by a hunter for a hunting experience and trophy. The most common trophy is the mounted head with horns or antlers, although other parts of animal body (e.g., skins, tails, teeth, heads) or even the whole bodies can be also appreciated as a trophy (see Chapter 3).

U**Uncertainty**

Any situation in which the current state of knowledge is such that:

1. the order or nature of things is unknown,
2. the consequences, extent, or magnitude of circumstances, conditions, or events is unpredictable, and
3. credible probabilities to possible outcomes cannot be assigned.

Uncertainty can result from lack of information or from disagreement about what is known or even knowable. Uncertainty can be represented by quantitative measures (e.g., a range of values calculated by various models) or by qualitative statements (e.g., reflecting the

judgment of a team of experts) (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Units of analysis

The IPBES Units of Analysis result from subdividing the Earth's surface into units solely for the purposes of analysis. The following have been identified as IPBES units of analysis globally:

Terrestrial:

- Tropical and subtropical dry and humid forests
- Temperate and boreal forests and woodlands
- Mediterranean forests, woodlands and scrub
- Tundra and High Mountain habitats
- Tropical and subtropical savannas and grasslands
- Temperate Grasslands
- Deserts and xeric shrublands
- Wetlands – peatlands, mires, bogs
- Urban/Semi-urban
- Cultivated areas (incl. cropping, intensive livestock farming etc.)

Aquatic, including both marine and freshwater:

- Cryosphere
- Aquaculture areas
- Inland surface waters and water bodies/ freshwater
- Shelf ecosystems (neritic and intertidal/littoral zone)
- Open ocean pelagic systems (euphotic zone)
- Deep-Sea
- Coastal areas intensively used for multiple purposes by humans

These IPBES terrestrial and aquatic units of analysis serve as a framework for comparison within and across assessments and represent a pragmatic solution. The IPBES terrestrial and aquatic units of analysis are not intended to be prescriptive for other purposes than those of IPBES assessments. They are likely to evolve as the work of IPBES develops (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Upwelling

A process in which deep, cold water rises toward the surface replacing warmer water pushed away by winds. Water that rises to the surface as a result of upwelling is typically colder and rich in nutrients, which

“fertilize” surface waters, meaning that these surface waters often have high biological productivity (NOAA, 2018b).

Urbanization

The increase in the proportion of a population living in urban areas; the process by which a large number of people becomes permanently concentrated in relatively small areas, forming cities (OECD, 2001b).

Use of wild species

The wild species uses are defined through the practices of fishing, gathering, terrestrial animal harvesting, logging, and non-extractive practices. For the purposes of this assessment, the use of wild species have been divided into different categories, which are not mutually exclusive: ceremony and ritual expression, decorative and aesthetic, energy, food and feed, learning and education, materials and construction, medicine and hygiene, recreation and other: e.g., companionship (see Chapter 1).

V

Values

Value systems: Set of values according to which people, societies and organizations regulate their behavior. Value systems can be identified in both individuals and social groups (Pascual *et al.*, 2017).

- Value (as principle): A value can be a principle or core belief underpinning rules and moral judgments. Values as principles vary from one culture to another and also between individuals and groups (IPBES, 2015).
- Value (as preference): A value can be the preference someone has for something or for a particular state of the world. Preference involves the act of making comparisons, either explicitly or implicitly. Preference refers to the importance attributed to one entity relative to another one (IPBES, 2015).
- Value (as importance): A value can be the importance of something for itself or for others, now or in the future, close by or at a distance. This importance can be considered in three broad classes. 1. The importance that something has subjectively, and may be based on experience. 2. The importance that something has in meeting objective needs. 3. The intrinsic Please do not

cite, quote or circulate 1733 value of something (IPBES, 2015).

- Value (as measure): A value can be a measure. In the biophysical sciences, any quantified measure can be seen as a value (IPBES, 2015).
- Non-anthropocentric value: A non-anthropocentric value is a value centered on something other than human beings. These values can be non-instrumental or instrumental to non-human ends (IPBES, 2015).
- Intrinsic value: This concept refers to inherent value, that is the value something has independent of any human experience or evaluation. Such a value is viewed as an inherent property of the entity and not ascribed or generated by external valuing agents (Pascual *et al.*, 2017).
- Anthropocentric value: The value that something has for human beings and human purposes (Pascual *et al.*, 2017).
- Instrumental value: The value attributed to something as a means to achieving a particular end (Pascual *et al.*, 2017).
- Non-instrumental value: The value attributed to something as an end in itself, regardless of its utility for other ends.
- Relational value: The values that contribute to desirable relationships, such as those among people or societies, and between people and nature, as in “Living in harmony with nature” (IPBES, 2015).
- Integrated valuation: The process of collecting, synthesizing, and communicating knowledge about the ways in which people ascribe importance and meaning of Nature’s contributions to people, to facilitate deliberation and agreement for decision making and planning (Pascual *et al.*, 2017).

Vulnerable population

Those individuals or groups who have a greater probability than the population as a whole of being harmed and experiencing an impaired quality of life because of social, environmental, health, or economic conditions or policies (FAO, 2021).

W

Welfare

See ‘Social welfare’.

Well-being (human)

Human well-being is a state in which there is opportunity for satisfying social relationships and “where human needs are met, where one can act meaningfully to pursue one’s goals and where one enjoys a satisfactory quality of life” (Gough & McGregor, 2007). Also see “Good Quality of Life”.

Western science

(Also called modern science, Western scientific knowledge or international science) is used in the context of the IPBES conceptual framework as a broad term to refer to knowledge typically generated in universities, research institutions and private firms following paradigms and methods typically associated with the ‘scientific method’ consolidated in Post-Renaissance Europe on the basis of wider and more ancient roots. It is typically transmitted through scientific journals and scholarly books. Some of its central tenets are observer independence, replicable findings, systematic scepticism, and transparent research methodologies with standard units and categories (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Wetlands

Areas that are subject to inundation or soil saturation at a frequency and duration, such that the plant communities present are dominated by species adapted to growing in saturated soil conditions, and/or that the soils of the area are chemically and physically modified due to saturation and indicate a lack of oxygen; such areas are frequently termed peatlands, marshes, swamps, sloughs, fens, bogs, wet meadows, etc. (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

Wild food

Wild foods are food products obtained from non-domesticated species (FAO, 2019).

Wild habitat

See “Natural habitat”

Wild meat

Wild meat is defined as meat for human consumption derived from wild species (see Chapter 3).

Wild relative

Wild species related to crops, including crop progenitors (FAO, 2018a).

Wild species

Wild species refers to populations of any species that have not been domesticated through multigenerational selection for particular traits, and which can survive independently of human intervention that may occur in any environment. This does not imply a complete absence of human management and recognizes various intermediate states between wild and domesticated. This assessment excludes feral and introduced populations (see Chapter 1, the definition is further explored in section 1.3.2).

Wild species watching (or wildlife watching)

Wild species watching is defined as a non-extractive practice where humans observe, and in some cases interact, with wild species in their natural environment in a way that does not involve the harvest or removal of any part of the organism. Wild species watching activities vary greatly in the level of wild species involvement, ranging from photographing animals from afar to more invasive practices of habituating, feeding and touching animals (UNEP/CMS, 2006, p. 2006). Wild species watching also is an economically important segment of nature-based tourism (see Chapter 2).

Wilderness

Ecosystems, landscapes and seascapes with a very low degree of human influence, at present with full recognition that they are often inhabited and managed by people, and have been so for centuries or millennia, often at low population densities, and therefore their native biodiversity and ecological and evolutionary processes have not been reconfigured by human drivers to a significant degree (Kormos *et al.*, 2017; Potapov *et al.*, 2017; Watson *et al.*, 2016). Not all areas designated as wilderness conform to this definition, especially in Europe where abandoned agricultural areas 'managed' by 'wild living' large herbivores are also called wilderness. Some wilderness areas in the world show transition to cultural landscapes with low human influence.

Willingness-to-accept (WTA)

Estimate of the amount people are prepared to accept in exchange for a certain state or good (e.g., WTA for protection of an endangered species) (IUCN, 2012a).

Willingness-to-pay (WTP)

Estimate of the amount people are prepared to pay in exchange for a certain state or good (e.g., WTP for protection of an endangered species) (IUCN, 2012a).

Worldviews

Worldviews defined by the connections between networks of concepts and systems of knowledge, values, norms and beliefs. Individual person's worldviews are molded by the community the person belongs to. Practices are embedded in worldviews and are intrinsically part of them (e.g., through rituals, institutional regimes, social organization, but also in environmental policies, in development choices, etc.) (IPBES, 2019).

Z**Zoonotic disease**

Zoonotic disease or zoonoses are directly transmitted from animals to humans *via* various routes of transmission (e.g., air – influenza; bites and saliva – rabies) (IPBES core glossary, 2021).

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